

**Revisiting Old Records:
Knut Lundmark's Studies in Historical Astronomy**

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Abstract

Historical astronomy, also called applied historical astronomy, was first proposed as a research method by Thomas Yeates in the early 19th century. The method involves collecting astronomical data from historical records and comparing those data with modern observations to address long-term questions in astronomy. In ancient China, celestial records were often referred to as *ce bu* (測簿), *hou bu* (候簿), or *ce hou bu* (測候簿), meaning measurement books, observation books, and observation-and-measurement books, respectively. With their long observation periods, systematic content, and strong continuity, these records have supported the study of long-term astronomical activities.

In the 1920s, Knut Lundmark (1889–1958) became the first researcher to bring ancient celestial records into modern astronomical inquiry, applying them to problems of celestial evolution. His work became a classic case in historical astronomy. Drawing on relevant historical materials and the writings of Lundmark and his contemporaries, this thesis aims to offer an in-depth understanding of the formation, methodology, and limitations of historical astronomy through textual analysis, case studies, and comparative research.

This thesis consists of six chapters.

Chapter 1 introduces and analyzes the academic literature on ancient East Asian celestial records and their applications, along with research on Lundmark. The literature review shows that case-specific studies remain relatively scarce and that the field of historical astronomy still offers considerable room for further exploration. For this reason, this thesis takes Lundmark's work in historical astronomy as its research object, with the aim of supplementing the existing literature.

Chapter 2 reviews the collation, study, and application of East Asian celestial records before Lundmark. It divides the early collation, translation, and preliminary examination of these records into three stages and identifies two stages of historical astronomical research within the broader development of astronomy. The early stage focused primarily on celestial mechanics; the modern stage focused on using ancient celestial records to address problems in astrophysics.

Chapter 3 provides a detailed account of Lundmark's life and his research achievements in historical astronomy. His interests in astrophysics led him to ancient celestial records, and he conducted his investigations under the influence of earlier scholars. These ancient records supported his research and became important sources for his popular science writing and literary work.

Chapters 4 and 5 present case studies of Lundmark's collation of ancient celestial records and his use of those records in stellar evolution research. Together, these chapters show how the records helped solve astronomical problems and how they continue to offer valuable data for modern astronomical research.

Chapter 6 reviews Lundmark's research achievements and contributions to astronomy, identifying both his influence and the problems that remain in his work. It also analyzes the reliability of East Asian historical observational records, recommending that researchers attend to observational accuracy, transcription errors, and cultural interpretation. Records from different sources should be compared, and modern scientific methods should be applied to evaluate their reliability so that they can be better understood and applied.

Drawing on the study of Lundmark's work in historical astronomy, this thesis concludes that his attention to ancient celestial records stemmed from his interest in both culture and astronomy.

Building on the work of Humboldt, Zinner, and others, he was the first to emphasize the importance of ancient celestial records for questions of celestial and cosmic evolution. He used ancient guest star records and stellar luminosity records to investigate these problems and sought to popularize this research method. His findings and methodology have been widely adopted in modern astronomical research, advancing several related fields. Even so, researchers must exercise caution when collating and studying these ancient records to ensure that their results are reliable.

Keywords: Knut Lundmark, historical astronomy, ancient celestial records, guest stars, novae

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

The development of astronomy depends on the accumulation of long-term observations, and historical archives are therefore essential resources. East Asian countries have a long tradition of astronomical observation. Original records in ancient China were often referred to as *ce bu*, *hou bu*, or *ce hou bu* (measurement books, observation books, and observation-and-measurement books). These celestial records, often preserved in historical documents, are abundant, span a wide time range, and remain largely consistent across sources, which makes them straightforward to interpret. Historical records document six to eight supernovae in the Milky Way, supporting research on stellar and cosmic evolution. East Asian records of sunspots, comets, and solar and lunar eclipses also offer crucial support for studies of long-period astronomical phenomena such as solar activity, cometary orbits, and changes in Earth's rotation.

During the 17th and 18th centuries, as economic and cultural exchanges between East and West increased, missionaries and sinologists began to take notice of ancient Chinese celestial records (Han, 1997). They organized, translated, and conducted preliminary examinations of these records, laying the foundation for later applications in astronomy and historical chronology. In 1921, building on this earlier work, the Swedish astronomer Knut Lundmark (1889–1958) recognized the importance of ancient East Asian guest star records for modern astronomy. In his study of suspected nova records, he investigated the reliability of the historical materials and sought to apply them to questions of celestial evolution. Lundmark's research marked the first application of ancient guest star records to astronomical inquiry. He went on to use East Asian observational records to explore the relationship between novae and nebulae, long-term

variations in starlight, and the statistical frequency of nova and supernova eruptions. These records provided significant support for his work, and he came to regard them as valuable resources. He saw their use in addressing related problems as a methodology worth integrating into astronomical research, an approach he called historical astronomy.

Taking Lundmark's work in historical astronomy as a case study, this thesis analyzes the prior research he drew upon and the methods he used, in order to trace the origins of his research ideas. It situates his work in the historical context of contemporary astronomy, examines the issues, impacts, and reliability of his research, and offers a preliminary evaluation. The thesis also introduces Lundmark's life and his contributions to the history of astronomy and to historical astronomy, with the aim of supplementing existing scholarship.

1.2 Previous Research

Previous research related to this thesis can be divided into three areas: studies of the application value of ancient celestial records, research on historical astronomy as a field, and studies of Lundmark's life and achievements.

First, regarding the application value of ancient celestial records, scholars have offered extended discussions of ancient East Asian materials. Needham and Wang (1995), in volume 3 of *Science and Civilization in China*, introduce Chinese records of eclipses, novae, comets, and sunspots and discuss their research and application value. Researchers have used ancient East Asian celestial records as case studies in astronomical research. Clark and Stephenson (2013) discuss the role of historical celestial records in supernova research in *The Historical Supernovae*. In *Applications of Early Astronomical Records*, Stephenson and Clark (1978) analyze the contributions of different civilizations, predominantly Asian, to early astronomical records,

examine the accuracy of these records, and discuss their importance for research on Earth's rotation and on supernovae. Stephenson (1997), in *Historical Eclipses and Earth's Rotation*, and Stephenson and Green (2002), in *Historical Supernovae and Their Remnants*, address the application of pre-telescopic solar eclipse data to studies of Earth's rotation and the contributions of newly discovered East Asian historical materials to supernova research, respectively. Beech (2016), in *The Pillars of Creation*, introduces the history of historical supernova research, while Powell (2019), in *From Cave Art to Hubble*, analyzes the application of historical East Asian astronomical observation data in supernova and comet research and discusses the significance and value of historical astronomy.

Second, regarding the concept and use of historical astronomy as a field, the term itself can be traced to the early 19th century. Yeates (1820), in an article on the lunar cycle, first proposed historical astronomy as a term for the method of collecting astronomical data from historical records and comparing them with current observations. Steele (2004) examines this method from a historical perspective, arguing that such research should focus on the application of early astronomical records to modern science and should interpret celestial records from different cultural backgrounds while verifying their authenticity.

The institutionalization of this research field is marked by the founding of the Historical Astronomy Division of the American Astronomical Society in 1980. In 1999, the American astronomer Katherine Bracher introduced the Historical Astronomy Division in an article that detailed its founding, development, main areas of work, and future prospects, and summarized numerous achievements in historical astronomy up to that point (DeVorkin, 1999). Wu (2012) used the research of Lundmark and Xi Zezong as case studies to examine the definition, origins, research ideas, methods, and evolving approaches of historical astronomy.

Third, regarding research on Lundmark's life and achievements, Sundman (1988) wrote the first biography of Lundmark, *Den befriade himlen*, drawing on archival materials. Sundman details Lundmark's upbringing, his research during his doctoral studies, and his work in popularizing astronomy. Holmberg (1999), in his doctoral dissertation, and Kärnfelt (2009) discuss Lundmark's achievements in galactic astronomy, astronomy popularization, and education. Both Kärnfelt and Sundman mention Lundmark's contributions to historical astronomy. Way (2013) analyzes Lundmark's contributions to the island universe theory and the relationship between galaxy distances and redshift. Teerikorpi (2007) wrote about Lundmark for the *Biographical Encyclopedia of Astronomers* and previously studied Lundmark's unpublished nebula classification method (Teerikorpi, 1989).

In summary, although scholars have examined the application of ancient East Asian celestial records in astronomy, existing studies typically focus on the overall development of specific subfields, such as historical supernova research or work on historical eclipse and sunspot records. These studies often require further analysis of specific cases. Research on historical astronomy as a field is similarly limited, with comprehensive studies appearing mainly in the works of Stephenson and colleagues and in Powell (2019). Existing studies of Lundmark concentrate on his achievements in galactic astronomy and astronomy popularization, with only limited attention to his contributions to historical astronomy and his use of ancient celestial records.

As an early body of work in historical astronomy, Lundmark's research offers methodological references for later scholars. Studying his achievements in this field demonstrates the significant value of historical observational records in modern astronomical research. Analyzing the issues

in his research also helps identify solutions to similar problems and supplements existing scholarship on Lundmark.

1.3 Research Objectives

The objectives of this thesis are as follows.

First, to examine how the problems addressed by East Asian celestial records have evolved from early research to modern applications, along with the development of research methods.

Second, to conduct a detailed investigation and review of Knut Lundmark's research in historical astronomy. Specific cases are analyzed from the perspective of the history of science, and a preliminary evaluation is offered.

Third, to investigate the relationship between Lundmark's research and contemporary astronomical studies, the subsequent development of his work, and to summarize and analyze the application value of East Asian celestial records.

Chapter 2: The Early Collation, Research, and Application of Ancient East Asian Celestial Records before Lundmark

Human observation of astronomical phenomena has a long history. In ancient Greece, the historian Thucydides (ca. 460–400 B.C.) recorded a solar eclipse on August 3, 431 B.C., the earliest precisely dated solar eclipse observation described in a European source. In the 4th century B.C., Theophrastus (ca. 371 B.C.–?), a student of Aristotle, left the earliest known record of sunspots. In ancient Rome, Seneca (4 B.C.–A.D. 65) documented in *Naturales Quaestiones* a comet that appeared around 151 B.C., shortly after the death of the Syrian king Demetrius (?–151 B.C.). According to Arabic legend, meteors were torches thrown by angels at spirits longing for heaven. Ibn Hayyan (987–1075) included a record of a solar eclipse in A.D. 912 in his writings, and Ibn Ridwan (ca. 988–ca. 1061) documented the supernova of A.D. 1006 (see Stephenson & Clark, 1978).

In ancient India, records of extraordinary celestial events also date back to antiquity. The term *ketu* was used in the *Rgveda* (ca. 1500 B.C.) to denote sudden appearances of celestial bodies such as comets and meteors. The *Brhat Samhita*, an encyclopedic work on Indian astrology compiled between A.D. 485 and 587, examined celestial phenomena associated with *ketu* in greater detail. Varahamihira (ca. 505–ca. 587) distinguished among different types of meteors, describing them and arguing that such phenomena foretold the death of rulers and the collapse of kingdoms. The rulers of the Mughal Empire also placed great importance on unusual celestial events, which led to numerous records of solar eclipses, comets, and meteors in their chronicles from the 16th and 17th centuries (see Kapoor, 2022).

Ancient China, along with neighboring countries such as Japan and Korea, developed a unique observational tradition that treated extraordinary celestial events as sacred omens that could not be ignored. Chinese rulers emphasized observing celestial phenomena to predict fortune and misfortune, align human affairs with divine will, and govern in accordance with heavenly timing. The study of astronomy therefore had significant ties to royal authority and served as both its foundation and its symbol. Phenomena such as solar eclipses, comets, and guest stars were regarded as indicators of the Mandate of Heaven. The orderly movement of celestial bodies symbolized the emperor's legitimate rule, whereas unusual celestial events were often interpreted as challenges to imperial authority or as portents of national instability. This belief permeated East Asian history, shaping political decisions and social development.

Ancient Chinese authorities placed great importance on eclipses. For instance, *The Book of Documents* (*Shangshu*·Yin Zheng) recounts the legend of the astronomers Xi and He, who were executed for their drunken negligence in failing to predict a solar eclipse. The story underscores the weight placed on such phenomena. The term solar eclipse (*ri shi*) first appeared in *The Book of Songs* (*Shijing*), in the poem The Tenth Month, which states:

At the turn of the tenth month, 十月之交,

On the new moon day of Xinmao, 朔月辛卯,

The sun was eclipsed, 日有食之,

An extremely ominous event. 亦孔之丑。

That moon waned, 彼月而微,

And now the sun wanes. 此日而微。

The common people suffer deeply. 今此下民, 亦孔之哀。

These verses show that solar eclipses carried symbolic meaning in *The Book of Songs*. They were seen as ill omens, reflecting the poor living conditions of the people, serving as warnings to rulers, and foretelling the destiny of the state. This sense of an interconnected relationship between heaven and humanity was central to ancient Chinese thought.

In ancient China, court astronomers were tasked with observing, interpreting, and predicting astronomical phenomena. They meticulously documented anomalies in celestial events, noting their positions, timing, colors, and brightness. These observations were compiled into official historical records and served as valuable references for later generations. The records were used at the time to predict the nation's destiny and were also regarded as significant historical testimony to the development of the state.

Compared with those of other countries, the astronomical institutions of China, Japan, and Korea were supported by royal authority, which gave them a notable advantage in observational accuracy and completeness. This further reinforced the role of astronomical phenomena in the political and social life of these nations.

The following discussion focuses on the collation, study, and application of ancient astronomical records since the advent of modern astronomy.

The year 1543 is generally regarded as the birth of modern astronomy, marked by the publication of *On the Revolutions of the Heavenly Spheres* by Nicolaus Copernicus (1473–1543). Modern astronomy required substantial data to support its theories, and historical observations provided valuable information for that purpose. During this period, many astronomers, including Copernicus, Tycho Brahe (1546–1601), and Johannes Kepler (1571–1630), recognized the significance of historical astronomical records.

Copernicus drew on the celestial observations of Ptolemy and Al-Battani (868–929) while constructing his heliocentric model of the universe. Tycho Brahe collected and studied historical records of solar eclipses and comets to validate and refine his celestial model. Kepler analyzed the observational errors of naked-eye solar eclipses recorded by figures such as Witelo (Vitellio, ca. 1230–ca. 1280) and Aristotle (384–322 B.C.) and attempted to calculate the true diameters of the Sun and Moon. Drawing on historical records, Kepler also argued that comets were atmospheric phenomena and demonstrated that their tails always point away from the Sun (Thoren & Christianson, 1990).

Many later astronomers used ancient records of comets to analyze their physical characteristics, calculate their orbital periods, and predict their returns. Ancient records of solar and lunar eclipses were also used to study the Moon's motion relative to Earth and to evaluate the accuracy of calendars.

Historical data thus provide astronomical research with long-term observational records that help researchers verify and refine theoretical models, understand the evolutionary laws of the universe, and study the dates and cultural contexts of specific events. This methodology of addressing astronomical questions through ancient celestial records is known as historical astronomy. The focus of historical astronomy is closely linked to the priorities of contemporary astronomy. Drawing on the existing literature, this thesis divides historical astronomical research into two phases, the early and modern periods, with the early 20th century as the dividing line.

Early Period (Before the 20th Century)

Before the 20th century, astronomical research focused primarily on the laws of celestial motion and dynamics, within the domain of celestial mechanics. Related historical astronomy research

included studies of historical solar and lunar eclipses and Earth's rotation, analyses of gnomon shadow records and the variation of the obliquity of the ecliptic, and investigations of changes in comet orbits and their return periods.

After H. S. Schwabe (1789–1875) discovered the 11-year solar cycle in 1843, scholars such as Daniel Kirkwood (1814–1895) and John Williams (1797–1874) sought to reorganize historical sunspot records. Researchers such as H. Fritz and Joseph de Moidrey (1858–1936) recognized the significance of China's historical sunspot records for astronomy and meteorology. Their studies explored correlations between these records and phenomena such as auroras and droughts and represent key achievements of the early stage of historical astronomy.

Modern Period (20th Century Onward)

The early 20th century marked the advent of theoretical astrophysics. By the late 19th century, advances in telescope precision and the adoption of spectroscopic, photometric, and photographic techniques accelerated the development of astrophysics. Astronomical research expanded beyond the study of celestial motion to include investigations of the physical properties of celestial bodies.

By the early 20th century, the accumulation of extensive observational data and advances in theoretical physics gave rise to theoretical astrophysics, which focused on the internal physical processes of celestial objects. Physicists began to apply physical laws to astronomical research, using new theoretical models to simulate celestial structures and analyze their evolution.

Historical astronomy research in this period included studies by Ernst Zinner (1886–1970) and others on variations in stellar magnitudes. Researchers such as Knut Lundmark, Xi Zezong, and Clark and Stephenson conducted significant investigations into ancient records of novae and

supernovae. These works bridged ancient observational records and modern astrophysical inquiry, demonstrating the enduring relevance of historical data for contemporary astronomy.

Since ancient times, unusual events in the sky have drawn human attention, and many of these phenomena were recorded by observers from various civilizations. Among them, the rich and detailed celestial records in East Asian historical sources stand out as a crucial component of the ancient observational record. They have provided invaluable support for studying long-period astronomical phenomena such as changes in cometary orbits, solar activity cycles, and supernovae within the Milky Way that survive only in historical accounts.

During the 17th and 18th centuries, as economic and cultural exchanges between China and the West increased, missionaries and sinologists took notice of these ancient Chinese celestial records. They summarized, translated, and studied these accounts and brought them to the attention of historians and astronomers. Building on this groundwork, later scholars conducted more in-depth studies and consciously applied the records to contemporary astronomical questions.

This body of research contributed significantly to the development of astronomy and provided an important reference for later studies in historical astronomy (Han & Duan, 1997). Many of its findings remain valuable today. The following sections explore specific case studies to illustrate these points in more detail.

2.1 Early Compilation, Translation, and Preliminary Study of Ancient Chinese Celestial Records

The early efforts to compile, translate, and conduct preliminary studies of ancient Chinese celestial records can be divided into three stages by time period: the 16th to 17th century, the 18th to 19th century, and the late 19th to early 20th century.

2.1.1 16th to 17th Century: *Compilation and Preliminary Study*

During the 16th and 17th centuries, the focus on ancient Chinese celestial records lay primarily on compilation and initial examination. This work was largely undertaken by ancient Chinese astronomers, Jesuit missionaries in China, and other foreign missionaries. Their efforts played a significant role in the compilation of historical records and in the creation and reform of calendars.

Table 2-1. Compilation and preliminary study of ancient East Asian celestial records in the 16th to 17th century.

Researcher(s)	Work	Year (Chinese Era)	Content
Xing Yunlu	<i>Examination of Ancient and Modern Calendrical Systems (Gu Jin Lü Li Kao)</i>	1607 (35th Year of Wanli)	Compilation of solar eclipse records
Johann Adam Schall von Bell and Johann Terrenz	<i>Examination of Ancient and Modern Eclipses (Gu Jin Jiao Shi Kao)</i>	1634 (7th Year of Chongzhen)	Compilation and verification of solar and lunar eclipse records

During this period, the introduction of Western science into China began with the collaboration between Xu Guangqi and Matteo Ricci on the translation of Euclid's *Elements*. At the same time, the Datong Calendar was found to be inaccurate in predicting solar and lunar eclipses. To

address the need for calendar reform, Matteo Ricci requested that the Roman Catholic Church send Jesuit missionaries proficient in astronomy to assist with the task.

During the Wanli era, Xing Yunlu compiled records of solar eclipses from the Zhongkang period to the late Yuan dynasty in his work *Examination of Ancient and Modern Calendrical Systems* (Gujin Lüli Kao). Jesuit missionaries involved in the calendar reform also recognized the importance of solar and lunar eclipse records for calendrical studies. In the Chongzhen era, Jesuits such as Johannes Terrenz (1576–1630), Giacomo Rho (1593–1638), and Johann Adam Schall von Bell (1592–1666) were summoned to Beijing to participate in the compilation of the Chongzhen Calendar.

Johann Adam Schall von Bell and Giacomo Rho examined 21 ancient solar eclipse records and 12 lunar eclipse records in their work *Examination of Ancient and Modern Eclipses* (Gujin Jiaoshi Kao). These studies provided valuable references for subsequent calendar revisions.

During the 18th and 19th centuries, as exchanges between Chinese and Western civilizations increased, Western scholars recognized the cultural value of ancient Chinese celestial records. They also realized that these records could aid in solving astronomical problems as well as issues of historical chronology and the verification of historical events. Table 2-2 highlights representative research achievements from this period.

Table 2-2. Compilation, translation, and study of ancient East Asian celestial records in the 18th and 19th centuries.

Researcher	Publication Year	Work	Content
C.L.J. de Guignes	1782	<i>Alphabetical Catalog of Stars, and the Series of All Comets Observed in China from 613 B.C. to 1222 A.D.</i>	Compiled and translated records of comets observed in China from 613 B.C. to 1222 A.D.
Antonius Gaubil	1814	<i>Treatise on Chinese Chronology (Traité de la Chronologie Chinoise)</i>	Organized and analyzed ancient Chinese records of solar and lunar eclipses.
Pierre Huang	Early 19th Century	<i>Catalogue of Solar and Lunar Eclipses in Chinese Literature</i>	Conducted a complete statistical analysis of solar eclipse records in Chinese historical texts.
John Williams	1864–1865	<i>- Eclipses in the Shu Ching (The Shu Ching Eclipse) - Eclipses Recorded in Chun Tsew - Solar Eclipses Observed in China from 481 B.C. to the Christian Era</i>	At the invitation of Hind, investigated, translated, and compiled Chinese solar eclipse records.
Alexander Wylie	1867	<i>Eclipses Recorded in Chinese Works</i>	Compiled a comprehensive table of solar and lunar eclipse records based on historical sources.
George Biddell Airy	1884	<i>Comparison of the Chinese Record of Solar Eclipses in the Chun Tsew</i>	Examined and compared solar and lunar eclipse records in <i>Chunqiu (Spring and Autumn Annals)</i> .

In 1758, when the return of Halley's Comet became a widely discussed event in the astronomical community, De Guignes (1782) organized the comet records from the *Comprehensive Examination of Literature (Wenxian Tongkao)*. He identified the correspondence between Chinese asterisms and Western constellations and conducted a statistical analysis of the number of comets associated with each constellation.

In addressing historical chronology, Johann Adam Schall von Bell attempted to verify the credibility of the historical account of Emperor Yao's reign through astronomical calculations

and concluded that it was credible. Jesuit missionaries such as Martino Martini (1614–1661) and Philippe Couplet (1623–1693), along with scholars such as Nicolas Fréret (1688–1749), also conducted studies on the chronology of ancient Chinese history. Fréret, in particular, referred to *Examination of Ancient and Modern Calendrical Systems* by Xing Yunlu and sections of *Wenxian Tongkao* translated by the Jesuit Liu Ying. He analyzed the historical records of dates and celestial phenomena and calculated that the solar eclipse mentioned in the Yao Dian chapter of *The Book of Documents (Shangshu)* occurred in 2007 B.C. (De Guignes, 1782).

During this period, orientalists such as Andreas Müller (1630–1694), Jesuit missionaries such as Philippe Couplet, sinologists such as T. S. Bayer (1694–1738), and several astronomers also attempted to use ancient Chinese solar eclipse records. For instance, they analyzed the solar eclipse records in *Comprehensive Mirror in Outline (Tongjian Gangmu)* to examine their connection to the celestial phenomena reported during the crucifixion of Jesus (Lundbæk, 1986). These studies highlighted the long time span and high reliability of ancient Chinese celestial records and drew the attention of more researchers to their significance.

From the 18th to the early 20th century, advances in astronomy, particularly in celestial mechanics, gave rise to numerous new challenges. These included calculating the movement of the equinoxes, changes in the obliquity of the ecliptic, the problem of precession, and the study of the origins of meteor showers, cometary orbits, and their return periods. The resolution of these issues relied heavily on long-term astronomical observations and placed new demands on the compilation, translation, and interpretation of historical celestial records.

During this period, although many scholars continued to translate and interpret ancient celestial records primarily out of cultural interest, they increasingly recognized the potential astronomical

value of these records. They consequently undertook further efforts to organize and translate the observations, paving the way for their application in addressing emerging scientific questions.

Table 2-3. Compilation and translation of ancient Chinese celestial records (Part 1).

Researcher	Publication Year	Work	Content
Antonius Gaubil	1846	<i>Catalogue des Comètes observées en Chine</i>	Compiled and translated records of comet observations in China.
Jean Pierre Abel Rémusat	1825	<i>Catalogue des Bolides et des Aérolithes observées à la Chine et dans les Pays Voisins, tiré des Ouvrages Chinois</i>	Compiled and translated records of fireballs and meteors in China and neighboring countries.
E. Biot	1841–1846	<i>Catalogue Général des Etoiles Filantes et des autres Météores observées en Chine pendant 24 siècles depuis le 7ème Sicle av. JC jusqu'au milieu du 17ème de notre Ère</i>	Compiled records of meteors and atmospheric phenomena observed in China over 24 centuries.
		<i>Catalogue des Comètes observées en Chine depuis l'an 1230 jusqu'à l'an 1640 de notre Ère</i>	Compiled and translated Chinese comet records from 1230 to 1640.
		<i>Catalogue des Etoiles Extraordinaires observées en Chine depuis les Temps Anciens jusqu'à l'An 1203 de notre Ère</i>	Translated and examined records of guest stars in ancient China up to 1203 A.D.
John Williams	1871–1873	<i>Observations of Comets from -611 to +1640, extracted from the Chinese Annals</i>	Investigated comet observation records in Chinese literature from 611 B.C. to 1640 A.D.

Table 2-4. Compilation and translation of ancient Chinese celestial records (Part 2).

Researcher	Publication Year	Work	Content
John Williams	1871–1873	<i>Chinese Observations of Solar Spots</i>	Translated and analyzed records of sunspot observations in China.
Domenico Lovisato	1875	<i>Antiche Osservazioni Cinesi sulle Macchie Solari</i>	Translated and examined ancient Chinese sunspot records.
Alex Hosie	1878	<i>Sun-Spots and Sun-Shadows observed in China</i>	Translated and studied records of sunspots and solar shadows in ancient Chinese texts.
Joseph de Moidrey, Huang Pierre	1904	<i>Observations Anciennes de Taches Solaires en Chine</i>	Studied the history of sunspot observations in ancient China, confirming the 11-year solar cycle.
Ernst Zinner	1919/1920	<i>Zusammenstellung der neuen Sterne</i>	Translated and selected ancient Chinese records of guest stars.
		<i>Verzeichnis neuer Sterne mit ungenauer Ortsangabe, unter Einschluß der zweifelhaften</i>	Cataloged new stars with imprecise locations, including doubtful cases.

After 1801, Antonius Gaubil (1689–1759) translated the comet records from *Wenxian Tongkao* and the Imperially Commissioned Supplement to the *Imperially Commissioned Continued General Examination of Literary and Historical Records (Qinding Xu Wenxian Tongkao)* and *Comprehensive Examination of Literary Sources (Wenxian Tongkao)* into French in a manuscript preserved at the Paris Observatory. Rémusat (1825) translated records related to meteors and other celestial bodies from *Wenxian Tongkao* into French. In 1841, Édouard Biot, drawing on numerous Chinese documents and related Japanese historical sources, translated accounts of meteors and meteor showers from Tongkao, converted their dates into Julian calendar dates, and explored the periodicity of meteors. Biot also attempted statistical estimates of meteor observations from the Song dynasty.

Williams (1871) referenced the original texts of Tongkao and *Records of the Grand Historian (Shiji)*, translating Chinese comet observation records into English while correcting some issues

in Biot's translations. After Heinrich Schwabe discovered the 11-year cycle of sunspots in 1843, scholarly interest in historical sunspot observation records grew. Williams (1873) compiled and translated ancient Chinese sunspot records from *Wenxian Tongkao* and *The Book of Documents (Shangshu)* into English, creating a tabulated record. In 1875, Domenico Lovisato (1842–1919) translated Williams's sunspot table into Italian. In 1878, Alex Hosie (1853–1925) extracted and translated sunspot records from the *Imperial Encyclopedia of the Complete Library of Ancient and Modern Books (Gujin Tushu Jicheng)*. Hosie noted that these observations could fill a gap in Western sunspot observations prior to the advent of telescopes, contributing to the analysis of the relationship between sunspots and climate change. In 1904, Joseph de Moidrey and Pierre Huang (1830–1909) also translated and studied historical Chinese sunspot records (Needham & Wang, 1995).

In summary, the early compilation, translation, and preliminary study of East Asian celestial records can be divided into three stages.

First stage: This phase was closely related to the compilation of historical records and the reform of calendars. Researchers, primarily ancient Chinese astronomers and Jesuit missionaries in China, carried out the work.

Second stage: This phase focused on solving historical chronological issues and verifying historical events. During this period, East Asian celestial records were introduced to the West, and some orientalist and sinologists translated and analyzed these records out of personal interest or for the purposes of historical research.

Third stage: From this stage onward, the focus shifted to researchers in the field of astronomy and to sinologists interested in astronomy. They recognized the value of these

records for astronomical research and worked to organize, translate, and study them as primary sources for advancing the field.

2.2 Early Applications of Ancient Chinese Celestial Records

As the field of astronomy developed, many researchers came to see that ancient Chinese astronomical records provided long-term observational data on phenomena such as solar and lunar eclipses, comets, and sunspots. Once classified and organized, these records could serve as part of the observational data used to address scientific research problems. Tables 2-5 and 2-6 provide representative examples of these applications.

Table 2-5. Applications of ancient Chinese comet records in orbit calculation and period prediction.

Field	Researcher(s)	Year	Work	Content
Application of Comet Records in Orbit Calculations and Period Prediction	Alexandre Guy Pingré	1783	<i>Cométographie ou traité historique et théorique des comètes</i>	Used ancient comet observation records to identify Halley's Comet.
	Ernest Laugier	1842–1846	- <i>Note sur la première comète de 1301, 1378</i>	
			- <i>Mémoire sur quelque comètes Anciennes</i>	Used ancient comet observation records to identify Halley's Comet and confirmed its returns in 451, 760, and 1378 in the second work.
	E. Biot	1846	<i>Recherches faites dans la Grande Collection des Historiens de la Chine sur les Anciennes Apparitions de la Comète de Halley</i>	Used ancient Chinese comet observation records to identify Halley's Comet and attempted to verify its return period.
	Crommelin & Cowell	1908/1910	- <i>Perturbation of Halley's Comet in the Past</i>	
			- <i>Essay on the Return of Halley's Comet</i>	Used historical observation records to identify Halley's Comet.

Table 2-6. Applications of historical sunspot and celestial records.

Field	Researcher(s)	Year	Work	Content
Application of Sunspot Records in Climate Change Research	H. Fritz	1893	<i>Die Perioden Solarer und terrestrischer Erscheinungen</i>	Explored the relationship between sunspots and climate phenomena, finding that periods with more sunspots had fewer meteorological disasters and vice versa.
Application of Historical Observational Records in Chronology	Müller Andreas	1685	<i>De Eclipsi Passional Disquisitio</i>	Translated and analyzed records of a solar eclipse in A.D. 31 from Chinese sources to study its connection to the crucifixion of Jesus.
	S.T. Bayer	1718	<i>De Eclipsi Sinica</i>	Analyzed Müller's study and rejected the connection between this eclipse and Jesus' crucifixion.
	Christfried Kirch	1723	<i>Brevis Disquisitio de Eclipsi Solis</i>	Investigated and concluded that the A.D. 31 eclipse could not have been observed in Europe.
	Fotheringham	1919	<i>The New Star of Hipparchus and the Dates of Birth and Accession of Mithridates</i>	Used ancient Chinese guest star records to examine historical issues.

The early applications of ancient Chinese celestial records are concentrated in five key areas: records of solar and lunar eclipses for calendar revision, gnomon shadow records for studying obliquity changes, comet records for orbit calculations and return-period predictions, sunspot records for studying climate change, and the resolution of issues in historical chronology.

2.2.1 Application of Solar and Lunar Eclipse Records in Calendar Revision

The earliest records of solar and lunar eclipses in China date back more than 2,000 years. Researchers have extracted and organized these records, calculated the corresponding dates, and compared them with the recorded dates to identify errors in the calendar and make the necessary adjustments. The start time and duration of eclipses also help determine the length of the tropical

year, the time Earth takes to complete one orbit around the Sun. Researchers have used solar and lunar eclipse records to study the length of the tropical year and, based on their findings, to revise calendars. These records provide critical data for determining astronomical events and calculating the length of the tropical year, supporting calendar corrections.

2.2.2 Application of Gnomon Shadow Records in Studying Changes in the Obliquity of the Ecliptic

Chinese gnomon shadow records have facilitated the study of changes in the obliquity of the ecliptic, the angle between Earth's axis and the plane of its orbit around the Sun. Variations in the obliquity of the ecliptic significantly affect Earth's climate and the distribution of sunlight. Ancient Chinese astronomers used sundials to measure time and track seasonal changes. By analyzing changes in gnomon shadow lengths over extended periods, they could calculate the Sun's angle relative to the horizon, providing insights into variations in the tilt of the ecliptic plane over time.

Around 1732, Antonius Gaubil studied gnomon shadow observations recorded in ancient Chinese texts and found evidence that the obliquity of the ecliptic had decreased over time. Although Gaubil himself did not accept the idea of a changing obliquity, his research provided clear evidence for it. His findings attracted the attention of Pierre-Simon Laplace, who published Gaubil's manuscripts and emphasized that gnomon records offered crucial evidence for the theory of a decreasing obliquity of the ecliptic.

2.2.3 Application of Comet Records in Orbit Calculations and Return-Period Predictions

Ancient East Asian celestial records have contributed significantly to the study of cometary orbits and return periods. These records contain detailed information about comets, including

their time of appearance, brightness, morphology, and location in the sky. Such data have been instrumental in determining the positions of comets, verifying the periodicity of comets, and calculating parameters such as orbital paths, semi-major axes, inclinations, and directions. Comparing these records with later observations has enabled researchers to study orbital changes and predict future trends, thereby advancing celestial mechanics and improving the understanding of the interaction between comets and other celestial bodies.

Pingré (1783) was one of the earliest astronomers to attempt to identify Halley's Comet using ancient observation records. In his *Cométographie*, he used these records to study the comet's identity and orbital characteristics. Similarly, Herschel (1851), in *Outlines of Astronomy*, noted the precision of many ancient Chinese comet descriptions, which allowed for approximate orbit calculations. Herschel suggested that, in addition to Halley's Comet, other significant comets in history, such as the Great Comet of 1680, might also be periodic. He speculated that it could be the return of a comet observed in 1105, with an estimated period of 575 years.

Other researchers, including Ernest Laugier (1812–1872), John Russell Hind (1823–1895), Édouard Biot (1803–1850), Andrew Claude Crommelin (1865–1939), and Philip Herbert Cowell (1870–1949), also used ancient comet observation records to identify Halley's Comet and verify its return period. In 1843, Édouard Biot attempted to use the record of a comet observed on March 22, A.D. 837, in *Wenxian Tongkao* to test the hypothesis that a comet's tail always points away from the Sun (Powell, 2019).

2.2.4 Application of Sunspot Records in Climate Change Research

Sunspots are areas on the Sun's surface with lower temperatures, associated with intense magnetic activity. This activity disrupts the Sun's energy flow, reduces the solar radiation Earth

absorbs, and influences Earth's magnetic field. The effects, alter the Earth's atmospheric response to solar radiation, affecting temperature, atmospheric circulation, and precipitation patterns. Sunspot activity is therefore considered a factor in climate change, although the extent of its influence requires further study.

Ancient East Asian records of sunspots provide valuable data for studying solar activity. A significant early study was conducted in 1893 by H. Fritz, who investigated the sunspot cycle and its correlation with climate change. Fritz compiled and analyzed records of sunspots from Alexander von Humboldt's *Kosmos* as well as sources from China and Europe (Fritz, 1928). He used these data to explore relationships between sunspot maxima and phenomena such as auroras, grape yields, and extreme weather such as hailstorms. When Fritz's article was republished in 1928 in the *Monthly Weather Review*, the editors noted that astronomers and meteorologists seemed scarcely aware of the universal and intrinsic value of Fritz's work, which reached its peak in 1893 with his publication in Zurich on the study of solar cycles and terrestrial phenomena.

Following Fritz, many researchers compared sunspot records with other climate data, such as temperature records, to investigate correlations and propose hypotheses about the causes and mechanisms of climate change.

2.2.5 Application of Historical Observation Records in Chronology Research

The ancient recording systems of East Asia documented dates and positions of astronomical events and thereby provide crucial information for determining the timing of historical events and calculating their specific epochs. These records also help verify the authenticity of historical accounts.

By comparing reconstructed dates of astronomical events with dates in historical texts, researchers can analyze and determine the timing of historical events. For example, during the late Western Han dynasty, Liu Xin used celestial records described in ancient texts during the Conquest of Zhou by King Wu as a basis for calculating the event's specific year when compiling the Santong Calendar (Jiang & Niu, 2000).

Astronomical records also help verify the authenticity of historical events. By comparing recorded dates and celestial events in historical texts with actual astronomical data, researchers can identify errors and provide independent evidence for historical narratives. Studies by Müller and Bayer on the solar eclipse recorded in *The Book of Documents* and its alleged connection to the crucifixion of Jesus exemplify such work. Fotheringham (1919) also investigated the reliability of Chinese records of a guest star in 134 B.C. and a comet in 120 B.C. Using these records, he identified the 134 B.C. guest star as the nova observed by Hipparchus and determined the birth and ascension dates of Mithridates (135–63 B.C.).

In summary, early scholars had two main purposes for studying ancient Chinese celestial records: to satisfy their cultural interests and to take advantage of these records for solving specific problems. Scholars consciously collected, extracted, and translated ancient observational records, treating them as supplements to contemporary observational data or as historical evidence, thereby supporting their own research and that of others.

2.2.6 Research Methodology

In the first stage, the preparation stage, researchers extensively collected historical documents, focusing on sections related to celestial records. These were then systematically organized and translated. During this process, differences in calendrical systems among civilizations and

varying standards for correlating Chinese asterisms with Western constellations required researchers to perform conversions and calculations.

The second stage, the analysis stage, involved comparing records of the same event from different locations and sources. Researchers analyzed the reliability of these records and investigated the reasons for discrepancies in order to determine their accuracy.

The third stage, the application stage, built on the first two stages and often integrated the research with astronomy or other related disciplines. For example, historical comet records provided data on the timing, location, and orbital parameters of comets. In celestial mechanics, such information helped identify similarities in cometary orbits, establish return periods for individual comets, predict future orbital changes, and verify the reliability of existing comet theories. Historical sunspot records, combined with climatology, were used to analyze the relationship between solar activity and climate change, offering insights that could benefit human activities. Celestial records in chronology research helped match celestial events with historical events, supporting the determination of the era, timing, and reliability of historical occurrences and contributing to a more accurate understanding of history.

These efforts demonstrated the enduring value of ancient celestial records as tools for advancing knowledge in multiple scientific and historical fields.

2.3 Conclusion

This chapter first explored the history of human observation of extraordinary astronomical phenomena. Since ancient times, many civilizations have documented unusual events in the sky. In ancient East Asia, particularly in China, Japan, Korea, and neighboring regions, such events

were regarded as omens of great significance to national development and were therefore given considerable attention. The observation records from these nations, notable for their accuracy and completeness, provided long-term observational data for astronomical research. These records have been instrumental in verifying theoretical astronomical models, understanding the laws of cosmic evolution, and solving problems related to historical chronology.

Drawing on existing literature and the progression of astronomy itself, this chapter divides historical astronomy research into two stages, using the early 20th century as the dividing line. The early stage of historical astronomy research coincided with the emergence and development of celestial mechanics. During this period, historical astronomical records were extensively applied in studies related to celestial mechanics. The modern stage corresponds to the birth of theoretical astrophysics, during which historical astronomical records began to be used in research on celestial structures and cosmic evolution. Beyond astronomy, these records were also applied in meteorology, historical chronology, and related disciplines, demonstrating a close relationship with the development of those fields.

The chapter also reviewed the early compilation, translation, and preliminary study of ancient Chinese celestial records, dividing the process into three phases: the phase associated with calendar-making, calendar revision, and historical documentation; the phase focused on solving problems in historical chronology and verifying historical events; and the phase aimed at advancing astronomical research and other natural sciences through further compilation, translation, and study.

The chapter then categorized the early applications of ancient celestial records into five fields based on the problems they addressed: solar and lunar eclipse records for calendar revision;

gnomon shadow records for studying changes in the obliquity of the ecliptic; comet records for calculating orbital changes and predicting return periods; sunspot records for studying climate change; and historical observation records for solving issues in historical chronology.

Through specific examples, the chapter analyzed these records' contributions to contemporary scientific research. It also examined the two main motivations of early scholars in studying East Asian celestial records: cultural interest and the utility of these records as supplementary scientific data and historical evidence. The chapter outlined the research methodology of those scholars, which included compiling and translating relevant records along with converting their positional and temporal information; comparing and analyzing data to assess the reliability of the records; and using the records as supplementary observational data or historical evidence to address specific research problems.

Chapter 3: Lundmark and His Historical Astronomical Research

Knut Emil Lundmark was born on July 14, 1889, in Älvsbyn Municipality, Norrbotten, in northern Sweden, and died on April 23, 1958, in Lund, Skåne County, in southern Sweden (Kärnfelt, 2009a). As one of the pioneers of extragalactic astronomy, he was among the first to recognize that spiral nebulae are galaxies independent of the Milky Way. He also identified the Crab Nebula as the remnant of the supernova observed in 1054, and his work came close to anticipating Hubble's Law. Beyond his contributions to astronomy, Lundmark was an outstanding science communicator and historian of science (Hockey & Trimble, 2014).

Figure 3-1. Lundmark at the age of 19 in 1908. Photo: Wikimedia Commons.

The sections that follow draw on existing historical sources to introduce Lundmark's life, analyze the background of his research in historical astronomy, and examine his use of ancient celestial records in astronomical studies. The aim is to investigate the origins of his research interests, assess the contribution of historical records to his work, and highlight the value of historical observational data for modern astronomy.

3.1 The Life of Knut Lundmark

Knut Lundmark was born in 1889 into a farming family in Älvsbyn, Sweden. During his childhood, the family faced financial difficulties, but Lundmark managed to complete his education with the support of a loan from Johannes Nygren, the local parish pastor. Despite these economic challenges, he excelled academically in primary and secondary school, particularly in mathematics. His passion for learning remained undeterred.

Among all his interests, astronomy was his greatest passion, traceable to his early childhood. By the age of five, Lundmark had already learned to identify many constellations and was trying to gauge the distance to the sky by using terrestrial landmarks. He observed the Moon's surface and recognized its rough, mountainous terrain. During this period, he once dreamed of the Milky Way reflected on a vast, dark body of water, a dream that returned to him vividly when he first saw a photograph of the Milky Way (Johnson, 1961).

At the age of nine, a visit from a Jewish guest had a profound impact on him. The guest explained that the Messiah had not yet arrived and that Jesus was merely one of many prophets. This revelation troubled Lundmark and deepened his fascination with the night sky, particularly

with questions about the Star of Bethlehem and the Messiah. In his later research, Lundmark made numerous attempts to explain the Star of Bethlehem from an astronomical perspective. He searched for records of it in ancient Chinese archives and looked for traces of Tycho Brahe's supernova and the Star of Bethlehem at the Mount Wilson Observatory (Johnson, 1961).

In 1901, Lundmark purchased *Vår Himmel* (Our Sky) by Camille Flammarion (1842–1925). The book answered many of Lundmark's childhood questions about the scale of the universe.

Flammarion wrote that the scale of the universe is infinite, that nebulae are galaxies, and that the distances to other galaxies have yet to be measured (Sundman, 1988, p. 11). This work, based more on faith and expectation than on purely scientific findings, provided Lundmark with his scientific awakening. Over time, Lundmark himself became a prominent science communicator, writing numerous articles, delivering countless public lectures, and earning the title of Sweden's Flammarion (Sundman, 1988, p. 12).

Figure 3-2. Knut Lundmark (arrow) outside the school in Krokträsk at age 10.

In 1908, at the age of 19, Knut Lundmark enrolled at Uppsala University to study astronomy under the guidance of Nils Dunér (1839–1914), the director of the university’s observatory. Dunér had played an instrumental role in introducing spectroscopy and astrophysics to Swedish astronomy in 1878 (Kärnfelt, 2009a, p. 22).

When Lundmark began his studies, the future of astrophysics was still unclear. His first research paper therefore focused on the orbit of the 1802 comet, a subject rooted in classical astronomy, specifically celestial mechanics. Lundmark’s research interests later shifted toward astrophysics, which became the primary focus of his career (Holmberg, 1999, p. 90).

On July 24, 1915, Knut Lundmark married Birgitta Carlson (1886–1974), who was also from Älvsbyn and worked as a rural schoolteacher. The two had met in 1907, initially as friends, before their relationship grew into romance. Owing to Lundmark’s academic pursuits and financial pressures, the couple often faced long periods of separation and had difficulty spending time together. Even so, Lundmark’s love and longing for Birgitta never waned, and they maintained their bond through letters and brief reunions (Sundman, 1988, pp. 19–52).

After their marriage, Lundmark took part in numerous public science lectures to supplement their modest income. Birgitta and Knut’s home became a welcoming space for astronomers from around the world. Even after Lundmark’s death, Birgitta remained actively involved in organizing events for the Tycho Brahe Astronomical Society (Sundman, 1988, pp. 133–137).

Figure 3-3. Young Mr. and Mrs. Lundmark (Sundman, 1988, «Den befriade himlen»).

In 1920, under the supervision of Östen Bergstrand (1873–1948), Lundmark earned his doctorate in astronomy with a dissertation on methods for measuring celestial distances. He used the apparent diameters and brightness of nebulae, extremely bright stars, and nova eruptions as benchmarks. By analyzing the average absolute magnitude of several novae in the Andromeda Galaxy (M31), Lundmark estimated its distance at approximately 200,000 parsecs, or about 650,000 light-years, roughly one-quarter of the modern best estimate. This finding provided early evidence in support of the view that the Andromeda Galaxy is an extragalactic system, at a time when most astronomers doubted the existence of galaxies beyond the Milky Way (Johnson, 1961, p. 55).

In his research on the nature of spiral galaxies, Lundmark was the first to recognize two distinct types of novae: one of exceptionally high brightness, now known as supernovae, and another within the normal brightness range, now referred to as novae. His work played a pivotal role in determining the scale of galaxies and contributed significantly to our understanding of the size and structure of the universe.

The astronomer Fritz Zwicky (1898–1974) praised Lundmark’s contributions to extragalactic research as one of the most important achievements in the 2,300-year history of astronomy (Johnson, 1961, p. 55).

After earning his doctorate, Lundmark spent two years working at several major observatories in the United States, primarily the Mount Wilson Observatory and the Lick Observatory, with support from the Sweden-America Foundation. During this time, he continued his research on extragalactic systems (Johnson, 1961, pp. 105–144).

In 1929, Lundmark succeeded Carl Charlier (1862–1934) as Professor of Astronomy at Lund University. By then, the turbulent and vibrant 1920s had come to an end, ushering in an era of consolidation and preparation for a new phase in scientific understanding. Modern physics became central to astronomical research, bringing both a new perspective on atomic interactions and a fuller appreciation of the vast scale of the universe. By the 1930s, Lundmark had already completed his most significant scientific contributions (Sundman, 1988).

During the 1930s, Lundmark contracted tuberculosis, and by the 1940s he was also suffering from diabetes. In the final years of his life, his eyesight deteriorated further, and he struggled quietly with his declining health. Despite these challenges, he remained committed to fostering

connections with the international astronomical community and worked to establish Lund University as a center for computation and data processing (Sundman, 1988).

For many years, Lundmark dedicated himself to an extensive cataloging project on galaxies. By the time of his retirement in 1955, significant progress had been made, but his relentless pursuit of improvements meant the project was never fully completed or published (Svenskt Biografiskt Lexikon, 2007, pp. 337–340).

Alongside his work in astronomy, Lundmark made significant contributions to science communication and the history of science. He published 15 popular science books and wrote hundreds of articles for the general public. He was particularly interested in the cultural and cognitive impact of astronomy.

In *Från Kaos till Kosmos* (From Chaos to Cosmos), Lundmark explored how the development of astronomy has transformed human worldviews (Lundmark, 1934, pp. 234–252). Another of his works, *Astronomiska Upptäckter* (Astronomical Discoveries), focused on the history of humanity's exploration of the universe (Lundmark, 1951).

After years of studying the history of astronomy, Lundmark completed *Nya Himlar* (New Heavens) in 1943, a monumental work printed in only 500 copies (Johansson, 2025). Spanning nearly 800 pages, the book uses key figures and pivotal events in the history of astronomy as a narrative framework. It traces developments from early cosmological concepts to groundbreaking discoveries about extragalactic systems and details billions of years of galaxy formation and evolution. The book highlights the contributions of diverse civilizations to humanity's understanding of the cosmos (Lundmark, 1943).

In addition to his books, Lundmark published numerous articles on the history of astronomy. He conducted studies on such topics as Democritus's views on the Milky Way, ancient Greek cosmological theories, milestones in the history of astronomy, and the Copernican Revolution.

In the field of historical astronomy, Lundmark's most notable achievements include his work selecting and analyzing ancient East Asian records and his use of these records to study the distribution, luminosity, and eruption frequency of novae and supernovae (Lundmark, 1921). In the course of this research, he identified the positional consistency between the Crab Nebula and the supernova of 1054 and gathered additional evidence to confirm that the Crab Nebula is the remnant of that supernova (Lundmark, 1938). This discovery made a significant contribution to the study of stellar evolution. Lundmark also attempted to link the Star of Bethlehem to guest stars observed in China in 5 B.C. and 4 B.C., offering an astronomical explanation for the event (Lundmark, 1953).

Lundmark further investigated historical records of stellar magnitudes, comparing them with the Harvard Star Catalog. He concluded that the luminosity of stars had not changed by more than one magnitude over the past 10,000 years (Lundmark, 1932a). In 1934, he founded the Astronomical History Research Society, which advanced studies in the history of Swedish astronomy and in historical astronomy more broadly (Teerikorpi, 2007).

After retiring in 1955, Lundmark embarked on an extensive lecture tour across Sweden, sharing his knowledge of astronomy and cosmology with audiences ranging from small towns to large cities. He addressed a wide range of questions and emphasized the importance of public access to scientific knowledge. He was dedicated to fostering an appreciation of science among people from all walks of life.

In the spring of 1958, after returning home from one of his many lecture tours, Lundmark was hospitalized for a foot ulcer caused by diabetes. His health deteriorated as he suffered multiple infections, and he died on April 23, 1958. His wife, Birgitta, lived in Lund until her death in 1974 and was buried alongside Lundmark in Älvsbyn. In 1976, a memorial monument to Knut Lundmark was erected near their gravesite in Älvsbyn (Sundman, 1988, pp. 133–137).

Knut Lundmark was an exceptional astronomer who made significant contributions to the study of extragalactic systems, stellar evolution, and historical astronomy. He was also a prolific science communicator and historian. He delivered countless lectures, published a wide range of popular science works, and actively participated in the development of educational materials. He encouraged public engagement with science and helped advance astronomy education in Sweden.

In historical astronomy, Lundmark's research on ancient celestial records provided critical data for measuring galactic scales, analyzing stellar evolution, and studying the nature and eruption frequency of novae and supernovae. The following sections explore his contributions to historical astronomy in greater detail.

3.2 Motivations Behind Lundmark's Research in Historical Astronomy

Based on the available literature, Lundmark's use of ancient celestial records as a data source for his astronomical research can be traced to three key factors: his lifelong personal interest, the demands of his work in astronomy, and the inspiration he drew from the works of scholars such as Alexander von Humboldt and Ernst Zinner.

From an early age, Lundmark developed a profound fascination with the scale of the universe and with the phenomenon of novae, an interest that persisted throughout his life. In his later years, he expressed this enduring passion in a French-language paper discussing the Messiah. He thanked the translator of the paper, writing: “To my dear friend Dr. Carl Luplau Janssen, my gratitude for his effort in clothing my memories in the garb of the French language.” In the paper, Lundmark argued that the birth of the Messiah was intrinsically linked to the appearance of a nova. He reflected on the history of nova observations in various East Asian countries and discussed the subject in depth (Lundmark, 1954).

Lundmark’s strong interest in historical records of phenomena such as comets and novae is evident in his other writings as well. In 1937, he authored a play titled *I stjärnans skugga* (In the Shadow of the Star), which, through more than 50 scenes, narrates stories related to the history of astronomy during the relatively short period between 1572 and 1609. Using events tied to novae, comets, and other celestial phenomena as his narrative thread, Lundmark begins his story with the Magi following the Star of Bethlehem, Attila the Hun (406–453) advancing toward Rome under the guidance of a comet, and William the Conqueror landing in England illuminated by Halley’s Comet. The plot then focuses on the lives of figures such as Tycho Brahe, Nicolaus Copernicus, Simon Marius, and Galileo Galilei, all influenced by the appearance of novae. Through this narrative, Lundmark sought to demonstrate the relationship between human actions and astronomical phenomena. He believed that the universe profoundly influences human understanding and asserted that we all live “in the shadow of starlight.” This cultural interest led him to prioritize the study of nova observation history (Kärnfelt, 2009b).

3.2.1 Lifelong Interest in Novae

Lundmark's interest in novae spanned his entire career. Beginning in 1915, his focus on astrophysics naturally drew him to questions about nova evolution, where he recognized the importance of ancient observational records (Holmberg, 1999, pp. 90–130).

Lundmark's first paper in astrophysics, published in 1917, introduced a spectroscopic method for measuring the effective wavelength of spiral nebulae and presented its results. He subsequently conducted extensive research on the positions of globular clusters and spiral nebulae within galaxies. In his doctoral dissertation, Lundmark used the total magnitudes of globular clusters to estimate their relative parallaxes. He also discussed the discovery of novae within spiral nebulae, analyzed their light curves, and suggested that these novae resembled those within the Milky Way and could potentially share the same maximum absolute magnitudes. On this basis, he used novae to estimate the average parallaxes of different nebulae. In his later research, Lundmark continued to use novae as tools for measuring the distances to spiral galaxies. The method supported the island universe hypothesis. At the Mount Wilson Observatory, Lundmark extended Herbert Curtis's (1872–1942) approach, comparing the luminosity of novae in the Andromeda Galaxy with those in the Milky Way. He concluded that the distance to the Andromeda Galaxy was approximately 650,000 light-years (Holmberg, 1999, pp. 90–130).

3.2.2 Investigation of Nova Distribution and Historical Records

Between July 1921 and April 1923, Lundmark conducted a series of studies on the distribution, luminosity, and eruption frequency of novae. One of these investigations focused on ancient Chinese guest star records, which he published under the title *Suspected New Stars Recorded in Old Chronicles and among Recent Meridian Observations* (hereafter SNSR). In this work,

Lundmark analyzed the reliability of historical nova-like records and summarized their key details. He intended the research to aid in the study of the apparent distribution, average magnitude, evolutionary processes, and relationships of novae to other celestial bodies (Lundmark, 1921).

The SNSR study also spurred further research by Lundmark in historical astronomy. In 1932, he examined the average magnitudes of historical novae and concluded that the suspected novae recorded in ancient Chinese sources had higher average magnitudes (Lundmark, 1932b). He classified them as belonging to the upper class of novae, or supernovae, similar to Nova S in the Andromeda Galaxy. In 1938, Lundmark conducted further research on the connection between the Crab Nebula and the guest star of 1054. Drawing on Japanese historical records, he estimated its absolute magnitude at the time of the explosion and confirmed it as a supernova, identifying the Crab Nebula as its remnant (Lundmark, 1938).

Lundmark also conducted extensive investigations into the cultural contexts of nova records, using them to address issues in chronology. His work demonstrated the enduring significance of ancient celestial records in astronomy and historical studies (Lundmark, 1934, pp. 243–252).

Research indicates that the works of Alexander von Humboldt (1769–1859), Ernst Zinner (1886–1970), and others provided conceptual inspiration for Lundmark’s investigations of ancient East Asian celestial records. In 1932, in his paper *The Pre-Tychonic Novae*, Lundmark wrote:

Some thirteen years ago I discussed these cases in a paper. Using mainly the historical records of the Chinese, Humboldt had concluded in his *Kosmos* that there might have been 18 Novae between 134 and 1609 A.D. Another discussion was subsequently given by Zinner, who concluded that there might have appeared

22 Novae during the period 222–1783 A.D. In my paper, 60 cases from the period 134 B.C. and 1828 A.D. were discussed, of which 9 cases were excluded on various grounds.

The article referenced from thirteen years earlier is SNSR. Lundmark returned to the same theme in 1934, writing in Swedish:

Det påpekades redan av Alexander Humboldt i hans klassiska verk *Kosmos*, att de kinesiska iakttagelserna över kometer tydligen också innehålla några beskrivningar av objekt, som måste hänföra sig till nya stjärnor och ej till kometer. Senare har Ernst Zinner och författaren granskat det kinesiska materialet och försökt att sälla de nya stjärnorna från kometer. Uppgiften är icke lätt, eftersom de kinesiska observatörerna ju icke själva kunde skilja mellan nya stjärnor och kometer. I vissa fall är det icke möjligt att avgöra, till vilken kategori av objekt som de föreliggande beskrivningarna hänföra sig

(It was pointed out already by Alexander Humboldt, in his classic work *Kosmos*, that the Chinese observations of comets evidently also contain some descriptions of objects that must be assigned to novae and not to comets. Later, Ernst Zinner and the present author have examined the Chinese material and attempted to sift the novae from the comets. The task is not an easy one, since the Chinese observers could of course not themselves distinguish between novae and comets. In certain cases it is not possible to decide to which category of object the descriptions in question belong.)

(a)	134	B.C.....	in Scorpio.
(b)	123	A.D.	in Ophiuchus.
(c)	173	"	in Centaurus.
(d)	369	"	?
(e)	386	"	in Sagittarius.
(f)	389	"	in Aquila.
(g)	393	"	in Scorpio.
(h)	827	"	in Scorpio.
(i)	945	"	between Cepheus and Cassiopeia.
(k)	1012	"	in Aries.
(l)	1203	"	in Scorpio.
(m)	1230	"	in Ophiuchus.
(n)	1264	"	between Cepheus and Cassiopeia.
(o)	1572	"	in Cassiopeia.
(p)	1578	"	
(q)	1584	"	in Scorpio.
(r)	1600	"	in Cygnus.
(s)	1604	"	in Ophiuchus.
(t)	1609	"	
(u)	1670	"	in Vulpes.
(v)	1848	"	in Ophiuchus.

Figure 3-4. Distribution of novae listed by Humboldt in «Kosmos».

In ancient China, the term guest star (ke xing) referred to unusual bright points in the sky that were distinct from fixed stars and planets. Such celestial objects would suddenly appear like guests, remain visible for several days or weeks, and then disappear. The appearance of a guest star was often regarded as an omen of good or bad fortune and was used by astronomers and astrologers to predict future events. Guest stars were commonly associated with phenomena such as novae, supernovae, and comets. Comets were usually described in detail regarding their tails and motion, whereas other guest stars were more likely to be novae or supernovae.

Alexander von Humboldt was the first to systematically analyze and compile ancient Chinese records of guest stars in the third volume of *Kosmos*. He separated records of tailless objects

from those describing comets and concluded that between 1252 and 1800 the number of observed novae was far smaller than the number of comets. Humboldt briefly outlined the distribution of novae, examined records of their luminosity variations, and offered some explanatory commentary. In his analysis, he proposed four key points. The luminosity of novae might exhibit periodic variations. Novae sometimes appeared in specific locations, such as the novae observed in 945 and 1264, both located at the edge of the Milky Way; the connection between this phenomenon and hypotheses about nova formation proposed by Tycho Brahe and others remained unclear. Certain entries in European and Chinese records of novae were incomplete and presented issues that required further investigation. Finally, the appearance of novae might follow a periodic pattern: for example, Gerolamo Cardano speculated that the nova of 1572 was a reappearance of the Star of Bethlehem, and compiling a comprehensive catalog of novae was therefore considered necessary.

This analysis laid the foundation for future studies of ancient celestial records and their application in understanding nova phenomena (Humboldt, 1850, pp. 210–232). Humboldt's research significantly advanced the contemporary understanding of novae and raised questions for further study and discussion. It achieved the goal of disseminating knowledge while inspiring later scholars to pursue related research.

In *Zusammenstellung der neuen Sterne* (Compilation of New Stars), Ernst Zinner sought to build on Humboldt's first and second points. Zinner focused particularly on records of nova luminosity and spectral changes over time. He collected and compiled data on the luminosity variations of 38 novae and supernovae, starting from Tycho's supernova. Using spectral analysis and other modern astronomical techniques, Zinner argued that nova eruptions represent a process in stellar

evolution rather than a phenomenon caused by the friction of celestial bodies with dust or nebulae.

Zinner also emphasized that the appearance of novae had catalyzed the study of celestial variability, opening new horizons in astronomical research and reflecting changes in humanity's scientific understanding. To provide historical context, Zinner listed pre-Tychonic observations of novae in his paper, expanding its temporal scope and creating a more comprehensive account of nova research history (Zinner, 1919, 1922).

3.2.3 Key Insights from Lundmark's Research

Drawing on the works of his predecessors, Lundmark identified several key points.

First, ancient records, particularly East Asian accounts of comets and guest stars, include a significant number of nova records. These records share a similar apparent distribution with known novae. Lundmark suggested filtering them and using their apparent distribution as a criterion for assessing the reliability of suspected nova observations (Lundmark, 1921).

Second, by marking ancient novae and suspected novae observed in modern meridian observations, Lundmark proposed creating comprehensive lists of novae. Analyzing their relationships with nearby celestial bodies could fill gaps in existing observational data and support studies of nova-related cultural history. This approach could also address modern astronomical questions, such as those related to nova evolution raised in Zinner's work (Lundmark, 1943).

Third, some late-period novae were likely recorded simultaneously in Europe and East Asia. Humboldt noted, however, that Europe lacks records of a suspected nova from 1578. Lundmark

recommended investigating the reasons for such omissions through further analysis (Lundmark, 1921).

Fourth, differences in how records were translated and filtered by scholars such as Biot, Williams, and Humboldt could complement one another. Records from other countries about the same celestial events could also provide valuable insights. By comparing texts, researchers could more accurately determine whether certain objects were novae (Lundmark, 1921).

Fifth, nova luminosity changes may be accompanied by significant spectral changes, and novae may also have the potential to erupt again. To accurately calculate nova and supernova eruption frequencies, or to analyze why novae erupt in specific regions of the Milky Way, more data must be collected (Lundmark, 1943, pp. 149, 215, 598–607).

Knut Lundmark's interest in phenomena such as novae began in his childhood and remained with him throughout his life. His cultural curiosity and his astronomical research interests led him to focus on historical records of celestial events and to pay attention to the related works of scholars such as Humboldt and Zinner. At the same time, the research of his predecessors made him recognize that historical records could serve as a valuable supplement to astronomical research data. Lundmark hoped that studying ancient celestial records would help him address certain astronomical problems. His approach of using ancient astronomical records as a data source for research drew further attention to East Asian celestial records among later scholars and contributed to the development of historical astronomy as a field.

The following section presents specific examples of Lundmark's research using ancient celestial records.

3.3 Lundmark's Research Utilizing Ancient Celestial Records

Lundmark observed:

Ett flertal av astronomiens uppgifter äro tidsbundna i den meningen, att därest de ej utföras vid en viss tidpunkt, så kan aldrig den framtida forskningen reparera denna underlåtenhet.

(Many of astronomy's tasks are time-bound: if they are not performed at a given moment, no future research can ever make good the omission.)

That is, many of astronomy's tasks are time-bound, in the sense that if they are not carried out at a certain moment, future research can never repair the omission.

Lundmark conducted numerous research projects using ancient celestial records, addressing a variety of issues related to celestial bodies and cosmic evolution. His work demonstrated the significant value of ancient records in astronomical research. The problems he addressed can be grouped into four main areas: solving issues related to celestial bodies and cosmic evolution, studying the nature of novae and supernovae, investigating long-term changes in stellar luminosity, and examining historical events from an astronomical perspective.

3.3.1 Solving Issues Related to Celestial Bodies and Cosmic Evolution

Lundmark analyzed East Asian records of guest stars and verified their reliability. These ancient records helped him establish relationships between the distribution and spectra of novae and bright or dark star clouds, thereby contributing to the understanding of their evolutionary processes. When calculating galactic scales by combining parallax estimations for dark star

clouds, Lundmark also used ancient nova records to supplement known nova data and improve the accuracy of his calculations.

Table 3-1. Lundmark's research using ancient nova records to study celestial and cosmic evolution.

Table 1: Lundmark's Research Using Ancient Nova Records to Study Celestial and Cosmic Evolution

Field	Title	Content
Using Ancient Nova Records to Study Celestial and Cosmic Evolution	1921, October: <i>Suspected New Stars Recorded in Old Chronicles and Among Recent Meridian Observations</i>	Lundmark identified "suspected novae" from ancient East Asian guest star records and attempted to study nova evolution using these records.
	1922, August: <i>The Absolute Magnitudes of Novae</i>	The distribution of ancient novae suggested a connection with dark star clouds near the distant center of the Milky Way. Lundmark found that some novae had known apparent magnitudes before eruption, proposing that novae might originate from giant or dwarf stars.
	1922: <i>The Distribution of Novae</i>	Earlier research indicated that novae might be related to bright and dark star clouds, enabling distance estimations between clouds and novae through parallax calculations.

3.3.2 Studying the Nature of Novae and Supernovae

The extensive supernova records found in East Asian guest star accounts played a pivotal role in Lundmark's identification of supernovae as a distinct type of celestial phenomenon. By examining the distribution and average absolute magnitudes of these suspected novae, Lundmark concluded that the majority of historical guest stars in Chinese records were upper-class novae, or supernovae, rather than ordinary novae. Brightness data from Japanese records of the 1054 supernova also helped Lundmark confirm its supernova nature and estimate its explosion date.

Table 3-2. Lundmark's research on the nature of novae and supernovae.

Table 2: Lundmark's Research on the Nature of Novae and Supernovae

Field	Title	Content
Using Ancient Nova Records to Study the Nature of Novae and Supernovae	1923, April: <i>Some Facts and Suggestions Concerning Nova</i>	Visible novae were mainly distributed in Cygnus and Aquila. Ancient observations suggested concentrations in $\lambda_0 = 384^\circ$, but adjustments showed clustering at $\lambda_0 = 337^\circ$.
	1931: <i>The Pre-Tychonic Novae</i>	Lundmark supplemented his 1921 research, naming bright novae in East Asian records "Pre-Tychonic Novae," classifying them as supernovae.
	1935, February: <i>On the Novae and Their Classification Among the Variable Stars</i>	Lundmark discussed guest stars observed by Chinese astronomers, such as the novae of 1572 and 1064, suggesting they represented higher-class novae or supernovae.
	1938: <i>Was the Crab Nebula Formed by a Supernova in 1054 A.D.?</i>	Using Japanese records, Lundmark provided supplemental brightness data for the 1054 supernova observed in China. He concluded that the 1054 supernova explosion was caused by a white dwarf, forming the Crab Nebula.

3.3.3 Investigating Long-Term Changes in Stellar Luminosity

Through his study of historical records of stellar magnitudes, Lundmark concluded that human observations of stars and the relative colors of most stars had likely remained consistent throughout history. He also found that the absolute magnitudes of stars had not changed as rapidly as previously believed. These findings filled gaps in modern star catalogs and provided insights into the history of astronomy and the evolution of magnitude measurement techniques.

Table 3-3. Lundmark's research on long-term changes in stellar luminosity.

Table 3: Lundmark's Research on Long-Term Changes in Stellar Luminosity

Field	Title	Content
Using Historical Stellar Luminosity Records to Study Long-Term Changes	1926: <i>The Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes by Ptolemaios, Al Sufi, and Tycho Brahe</i>	Lundmark compared magnitude estimates from ancient astronomers with modern results, concluding that human observations of star brightness have remained consistent over time.
	1927: <i>On the Earliest Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes</i>	Lundmark reviewed ancient methods of observing and categorizing stellar brightness, analyzing whether significant changes had occurred over time.
	1932: <i>The Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes in the Star Catalogue in K'in-Ting-I-Hsiang K'ao-Tch'eng</i>	The <i>Qianlong Star Catalogue</i> included faint stars (5–6 magnitudes) absent from earlier star catalogues, providing a basis for studying 18th-century stellar luminosity changes.
	1932: <i>Luminosities, Colours, Diameters, Densities, Masses of the Stars</i>	Lundmark matched 3,083 stars in the <i>Qianlong Star Catalogue</i> to modern data, suggesting white stars become redder as their apparent magnitude increases.
	1932: <i>Secular Change in Stellar Light</i>	Studying 739 stars from Ptolemy's and Al Sufi's star catalogues, Lundmark found that stellar magnitudes varied by no more than one magnitude over 10,000 years.

3.3.4 Examining Historical Events from an Astronomical Perspective

Lundmark investigated the cultural significance of novae and comets, using them to verify the timing of historical events. His work proposed several thought-provoking ideas, some of which received widespread attention. By linking celestial phenomena to historical contexts, he offered innovative perspectives for understanding the past.

Table 3-4. Lundmark's research on historical events through nova and comet records.

Table 4: Lundmark's Research on Historical Events Through Nova and Comet Records

Field	Title	Content
Using Ancient Nova and Comet Records to Investigate Historical Events	1950: <i>On the Origin and Development of the Messianic Idea and the Eschatology of the New Testament</i>	Lundmark examined the symbolic significance of novae and comets, linking celestial events to cultural narratives about prominent figures, such as: 1. The Star of Bethlehem, corresponding to a suspected nova in 5 B.C. 2. Halley's Comet in 66 A.D., associated with Tiridates I's coronation by Nero. 3. A suspected nova in 123 A.D., which inspired Simon's revolt against Rome. 4. A nova in 532 A.D., potentially related to Buddha, Laozi, Confucius, and Zoroaster.
	1953: <i>The Messianic Ideas and Their Astronomical Background</i>	Explored the astronomical context of messianic beliefs and celestial events.
	1953: <i>On the Problem of the Origin and Evolution of the Messianic Idea and the Eschatology of the New Testament</i>	Investigated the relationship between historical celestial phenomena and religious concepts.

Taken together, Lundmark's work helped researchers better understand the context of ancient astronomical observations and appreciate the reliability of ancient records. His efforts demonstrated the feasibility of using these observations to address issues in both astronomy and history, offering valuable insights for solving a range of astronomical problems. His pioneering approach provided important clues for later studies in the field.

3.4 Conclusion

The first section of this chapter provided a detailed overview of Knut Lundmark's life and achievements, highlighting his contributions to astrophysics, science communication, the history of science, and historical astronomy. The discussion shows that Lundmark's focus on questions about novae and supernovae and the scale of the universe, as well as his interest in science communication, can be traced to his childhood interests. Throughout his career, Lundmark prioritized astrophysics and made notable contributions in such areas as the study of nebulae, galactic scale measurement, and stellar evolution. Historical observational records provided critical support for his astronomical research.

The second section investigated the origins of Lundmark's historical astronomy research. Lundmark's personal interests and research needs led him to focus on historical celestial records. Inspired by scholars such as Humboldt and Zinner, he conducted investigations of East Asian records of guest stars and historical records of stellar brightness variations.

The third section summarized Lundmark's research using ancient celestial records. These records provided data for measuring galactic scales and for studying the birth and evolution of novae, supernovae, and stars. They also enabled Lundmark to investigate historical events from an astronomical perspective and encouraged him to explore the cultural contexts of nova and comet observations in China and Japan. They provided valuable material for his science communication and literary works.

In summary, Lundmark's research demonstrated the significant value of historical celestial records in astronomical studies. The following two chapters examine representative case studies

from Lundmark's work in historical astronomy. They investigate his efforts in organizing ancient celestial records and analyze how he applied these records to solve specific problems.

The organization of historical records forms the foundation for their application to specific issues. This principle is evident in Lundmark's research as well as in other historical studies of natural science. Through appropriate classification and selection, Lundmark transformed historical records into data sources for his research. Chapter 4 analyzes his research process and the associated challenges and summarizes his methods. Chapter 5 focuses on the specific problems Lundmark addressed using these celestial records, situating his work in the historical context of contemporary astronomical developments. It discusses the issues he resolved and the methods he employed to address them.

After introducing Lundmark's research interests, origins, and specific achievements, the analysis turns to the impact of his work on astronomy from the perspective of the history of science and offers a preliminary evaluation of the historical value of his findings.

Chapter 4: Lundmark's Organization of Ancient Celestial Records

Lundmark's most representative research in historical astronomy focused on two areas: ancient guest star records and stellar luminosity records.

His investigation of ancient guest star records began in 1921 and marked the start of his work in historical astronomy. In *Suspected New Stars Recorded in Old Chronicles and Among Recent Meridian Observations*, Lundmark organized, filtered, and analyzed Chinese guest star records and supplemented them with contemporary nova observations. These records aided him and later researchers in addressing questions about cosmic scale and celestial evolution (Lundmark, 1921a).

In his studies of stellar luminosity from 1926 to 1932, Lundmark examined the star catalogs of Ptolemy, Al-Sufi, and Tycho Brahe, along with the *Qianlong Star Catalog* 《乾隆星表》. He converted the magnitude data in these catalogs into modern standardized values and compared them with contemporary measurements. Lundmark hoped that his work would contribute to understanding long-term luminosity changes in stars (Lundmark, 1926).

This chapter reviews Lundmark's organization of ancient guest star records and stellar luminosity records, analyzes his methods alongside related studies, and evaluates the reliability of his approaches. This evaluation provides a foundation for examining, in the next chapter, how Lundmark applied ancient celestial records to specific astronomical problems.

4.1 Previous Research on Lundmark's Contributions to Historical Astronomy

Several researchers in astronomy and the history of science have briefly introduced Lundmark's contributions to historical astronomy, analyzed his methods, and corrected certain errors in his studies. This section provides an overview of that work as a foundation for the rest of the chapter.

4.1.1 Introduction and Evaluation of Lundmark's Research Contributions

Needham and Wang (1995) noted in *Science and Civilization in China, Volume 3* that Lundmark's *Suspected New Stars* helped verify the reliability of ancient Chinese astronomical observations. Needham highlighted issues in Lundmark's research, citing his attempt to apply guest star records to historical events as an example. Needham argued that ancient Chinese celestial records held significant value for modern scientific research, while also pointing out interpretive errors by sinologists regarding guest star positions, errors that influenced Lundmark's work and that of later researchers.

Apparao (1973) referenced historical research in his paper *The Crab Nebula*, emphasizing the importance of textual analysis for understanding the nebula. He acknowledged that the earliest studies of the Crab Nebula grew out of translations of ancient Chinese guest star records and the historical astronomy research of Lundmark and others.

Clark and Stephenson (2013), in *The Historical Supernovae*, suggested that Lundmark may have been the first to recognize the greater significance of novae over comets in these records. They discussed Lundmark's work in *Suspected New Stars*, noting that it relied on secondary sources. The authors also reviewed his investigation of the connection between AD 1054 and the Crab

Nebula, along with his incorrect attribution of an imagined supernova in AD 827, which actually corresponded to the supernova of 1006.

4.1.2 Analysis of Lundmark's Research Methods

Wu (2012) provided a detailed analysis of the sources, objectives, methodology, and conclusions of Lundmark's *Suspected New Stars*. Comparing Lundmark's research with that of Biot, Humboldt, and Zinner, she argued that Lundmark deliberately used ancient guest star records and Western astronomical data to address questions such as the spatial distribution of novae and supernovae in the Milky Way within the framework of celestial evolution research. Wu identified a problem-driven approach in Lundmark's work.

By comparing studies of ancient guest star records across three distinct stages, Wu highlighted the development of historical astronomy methodologies. She concluded that historical astronomy leverages historical observational data to address modern astronomical questions, making it a genuine astronomical research method rooted in the history of astronomy.

4.1.3 Corrections and Supplements to Lundmark's Research

In the early 1940s, the Crab Nebula was identified as the remnant of the supernova of AD 1054. Later discoveries in the 1950s linked the supernovae of 1572 and 1604 to radio sources. Astronomers hypothesized that supernova explosions generate radio sources, but verifying this hypothesis required historical data. Lundmark's research proved insufficient in accuracy for this stage of investigation.

Xi (1955), in *A New Catalog of Ancient Novae*, revised Lundmark's records, corrected errors, and added new cases. He produced a revised distribution map of ancient novae, summarized nova distribution patterns, and compiled a new catalog using additional materials.

Ho (1962) re-cataloged Chinese comet and nova records, incorporating Korean and Japanese records. He further revised issues in the studies of Lundmark and Xi Zezong. In 1965, Bo Shuren collaborated with Xi Zezong to analyze nova records from China, Korea, and Vietnam, emphasizing their significance for radio astronomy. In 1970, Ho expanded his work with a comet and guest star list covering 1368–1911, providing thorough documentation and a star map of the East.

Zhou (2013) revisited Lundmark's contributions in *Reinvestigating Ancient East Asian Guest Star Records*. Zhou argued that Lundmark's research represented a complete integration of theoretical studies with the analysis of ancient records by a cutting-edge astronomer. Zhou reexamined several guest star records, proposed new interpretations for ambiguous cases, and included an updated catalog of ancient novae in the appendix.

Research Context and Contributions

Current literature reviews suggest that no dedicated studies focus on Lundmark's organization and application of ancient celestial records. Existing research provides brief introductions and analyses of his contributions to historical astronomy but rarely explores his work beyond guest star applications.

In the sections that follow, I extract additional examples from Lundmark's research, analyze their historical context, identify challenges, evaluate the reliability and impact of his methods,

and discuss his pioneering role in historical astronomy. I also propose solutions to similar problems based on Lundmark's work.

4.2 Lundmark's Organization and Filtering of Ancient Chinese Guest Star Records in Suspected New Stars

4.2.1 Content and Structure of Suspected New Stars

The structure of *Suspected New Stars* consists of a main body and an appendix. The main body is further divided into two parts based on the issues it addresses.

Table 4-1. Structure diagram of the body of «Suspected New Stars Recorded in Old Chronicles and Among Recent Meridian Observations».

Part I (paragraph 9, p. 225 to paragraph 4, p. 229) investigates and screens the suspected new star records. After reviewing the compilation, translation, and research of ancient guest star records by previous researchers, Lundmark examined the research backgrounds, sources, and reliability of the Chinese comet and guest star records translated by Biot and Williams, the materials to which he most often refers. During his investigation, Lundmark observed subtle differences in

the translations of different versions and recognized that careful textual study could improve the accuracy of identification. After excluding the comet and guest star records that mentioned tails and motions, Lundmark determined the probability that the remaining objects were novae according to their distribution, luminosity, and visibility. He then compared the distribution of suspected and known novae, mapped it, and concluded that the apparent distributions of suspected and known novae are close to each other and concentrated at the center of the stellar system. He inferred that most of these ancient guest stars are true novae. He also found that Chinese records of comets do not show any particular concentration on the galaxy, and he used this observation to exclude certain comet records that did not mention motion.

Part II (paragraph 5, p. 229 to p. 232) builds on these conclusions and on the astronomical findings of the time (that the apparent distribution of novae has a specific pattern and that novae may appear in the vicinity of nebulae). Lundmark sought to establish relationships between these ancient novae and nearby objects, contributing to the study of their connections with stars, nebulae, Wolf-Rayet stars, and irregular variable stars. He argued that further studies are needed to understand the true evolution of novae and that the evolution of celestial bodies and their positions in the galaxy also require further investigation. He noted that it would be valuable to search for planetary nebulae, Wolf-Rayet stars, or irregular variable stars in the locations of some of the objects mentioned in the article.

The article also has two appendices. In Part III (pp. 233–234, Appendix I), Lundmark organized his survey of suspected nova records into a List of Suspected Novae, in which he indicated the epoch, position, inferred coordinates, time of visibility (in months), and maximum brightness, and attempted to infer the probability that these objects were novae. The 60 objects in this list

include 54 suspected novae from historical records and 6 suspected novae from recent meridian observations.

Part IV (pp. 235–238, Appendix II) consists of the paper’s remarks. Like the explanatory comments made by Humboldt after a brief statement on the distribution of novae, this part contains Lundmark’s discussions of some cases in the List of Suspected Novae. For controversial cases, Lundmark presented the views of different scholars for reference and offered his own judgment in some of them.

In contrast to the Chinese historical records of comets, which had received extensive attention in previous studies, Lundmark first noticed the importance of ancient astronomical records in modern astronomical research and found that some of the problems addressed in earlier studies resembled those he faced in his own astronomical research. He therefore collected historical astronomical records and applied research results from contemporary astronomy as a tool to examine the validity of these records and to use them to address problems related to the evolution of celestial bodies and the distribution of novae. This work marked the beginning of modern research on the ancient guest star records of East Asia.

4.2.2 Lundmark’s Method for Determining Novae and Its Reliability

In *Suspected New Stars*, Lundmark introduced his method for determining whether a celestial object was a nova:

In the Chinese records of comets, “Ke-Sings” (strange stars, étoiles-hôtes) are frequently mentioned. Biot has shown that often the observations in question were of comets without tails, since the reference was made to the motion of the object. Even where it is explicitly stated that the object had no motion and no tail,

occasional allusion may have been made to a comet. On the other hand, it has sometimes happened that an object in the heavens has been considered to be a comet when it really was a nova; for example, several authors mistook Kepler's nova of 1604 for a comet, and some of them moreover thought they had detected motion in the object. ... Sometimes it happens, moreover, that Williams has not mentioned cases given by Biot, so that the translations are supplementary to each other. (Lundmark, 1921a, pp. 226–227)

Drawing on the work of Biot and others, Lundmark observed that some entries in the Chinese comet records did not mention tails or motions, which suggested that these objects might be novae rather than comets. He therefore compared different translations in order to screen the possible novae among these objects.

In his description of the suspected nova of 48 BC, Lundmark analyzed Williams's translation "It was about 4 cubits in length" and Biot's translation "Elle était à l'est de la 2e étoile du Nan-teou (μ Sagittaire); elle pouvait en être éloignée de 4 degrés" (It lay to the east of the second star of Nan-teou (μ Sagittarius), about 4 degrees away). He concluded that this was not a description of a comet tail, and he assumed that other cases were similar (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 225).

In his description of the suspected nova of AD 70, Lundmark wrote:

Since the position and the duration of visibility are recorded, it is evident that the object was under observation. As no motion is mentioned, this fact favors the object being a nova. The same remarks apply to many other objects in the table. (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 235)

Accordingly, Lundmark used the presence or absence of descriptions of an object's tail or motion over an extended period to determine whether the object was a nova.

Lundmark collected information on the epoch, position, inferred coordinates, time of visibility, and maximum brightness of these suspected novae. He listed them in the table on pages 233 and 234 and attempted to infer the probability that these objects were novae, using 3 to indicate a high probability and 0 to indicate a low probability:

The table on pages 233 and 234 contains the data drawn from the sources described concerning the epoch of the outburst, the position in the sky, the brightness, and the duration of visibility. In column 10, the estimated probability is set down: zero indicates that there seems to be no probability that the object in question was a nova; 1 that it is rather uncertain whether or not a nova is referred to; 2 that the object was probably a nova; and 3 that the probability is very great that the object is a genuine nova. λ and β are the galactic longitudes and latitudes. (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 227)

In the record of a suspected nova in AD 369, Lundmark wrote:

Zinner interprets the information in the text as indicating that the position of the star was in Cassiopeiae or the neighborhood. This seems to be reasonable. The long duration of visibility makes it probable that the object was a nova, as the comets generally were not seen by the unaided eye for so long a time. (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 236)

In the records of AD 1203, Lundmark wrote:

The comparatively detailed description makes it very probable that the object was a genuine nova. The comparison with Saturn excludes every possibility of its being a comet and gives an estimate of the maximum brightness. (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 237)

For these two objects, Lundmark assigned a value of 3 in the list, indicating a high probability of being novae. This shows that he weighted such objects on the basis of brightness, position, and visibility.

Lundmark plotted the suspected novae in two tables according to their galactic coordinates. He showed the distribution of 41 known novae and 6 suspected novae observed in recent meridian observations. For comparison, he also showed the distribution of P Cygni stars and long-period variable stars (see Figures 4-1 and 4-2). Lundmark argued that the suspected novae are consistent with known novae in their apparent distribution (between galactic longitudes 320° and 330° , around the center of the stellar system), suggesting that most of the suspected novae are likely to be true novae.

Figure 4-1. Galactic distribution of 41 known novae (solid circles) and 6 suspected novae from recent observations (open circles), P Cygni stars (crosses), and some irregular long-period variables (crossed circles) (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 228).

Figure 4-2. Galactic distribution of novae from ancient records and meridian observations (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 228).

Additionally, Lundmark argued that suspected novae are likely to occur at the borders of bright nebulae or in regions where stellar density is comparatively low (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 229), just as known novae do. In Figure 4-3, he marked the distribution of known and suspected novae, arguing for the reliability of the historical data while also analyzing whether known and suspected novae are consistent with this view.

Figure 4-3. Curves of equal light intensity in the Milky Way (from Graff's paper in «Astronomische Abhandlungen der Hamburger Sternwarte», Vol. II, No. 5, 1920), with positions of known and suspected novae (Lundmark, 1921a, p. 230).

In summary, Lundmark's method for testing whether an object was a nova proceeded as follows. He first referred to previous translations of records of objects such as comets and guest stars, compared different descriptions, and sorted out objects for which no tail or motion was mentioned. He compiled the relevant information on the position, brightness, and duration of

visibility of each object and assigned a weight to each suspected nova, with higher weights indicating a higher probability of being a nova. He then analyzed the distribution of suspected novae and compared it with the distribution of known novae. He found that most of the objects in the list had a distribution similar to that of known novae, which supported the reliability of the screened suspected novae and led him to conclude that these objects were predominantly genuine novae.

Most researchers after Lundmark adopted a similar method for screening novae and supernovae in historical records. By careful investigation, they identified objects without tails or motions. By examining the consistency of the distribution of ancient and modern novae, they filtered out objects with a higher probability of being novae and listed them in their catalogs (see Chen, 2016; Ho, 1970; Stephenson, 1997; Xi, 1955). In *Pre-Tychonic Novae*, Lundmark proposed his criteria for determining the boundary between ancient and modern nova studies, namely the nova observed by Tycho Brahe in 1572. It has been argued that 29 of the 46 pre-Tychonic novae in Lundmark's List of Suspected Novae are reliable, which indicates that Lundmark's study has methodological reliability and reference value.

This type of research is based on rigorous examination and analysis of historical records, and the accuracy of its results therefore depends heavily on the accuracy of the historical sources consulted. In terms of documentary sources, Lundmark's information is mainly derived from the works of Biot and Williams. Xi (1955) points out that the research of Biot and Williams relies on Ma Duanlin's *Wenxian Tongkao*, which is not a complete summary of the astronomical records in Chinese history (Xi, 1955). On one hand, the lack of references caused Lundmark to fail to note the motion of some celestial bodies in question.

On the other hand, Biot and Williams, in their treatment of Chinese historical sources, did not draw sufficient distinctions among Hui Xing (Comets), Bei Xing (a comet whose light radiates in all directions), Ke Xing (Guest Stars), Zhu Xing (Candle Stars), and Chang Xing (Comets with long-shaped lights), some of which are aliases for comets. This led to imprecise translations and caused Lundmark to include some objects in his list that may have been comets. Additionally, there are other problems in Lundmark's study, such as the lack of recognition that some comets have long visible periods and the difficulty of determining the dates and positions of certain objects. These problems are reflected in Lundmark's investigation of the pre-Tychonic novae, which I analyze further in the following section.

4.2.3 Summary of Lundmark's Problematic Entries in the Suspected Nova Records

The early studies of East Asian comet and guest star records that Lundmark consulted in *Suspected New Stars* included the following five main items:

Biot (1846, pp. 44–68) compiled and translated the comet observations in China between 1230 and 1640, drawing on the *Tianwenzhi* (Treatise on the Heavens) sections of the *Song Shi* (History of the Song), *Yuan Shi* (History of the Yuan), and *Ming Shi* (History of the Ming). Biot also compiled and translated the guest star records in the *Ming Shi*.

Williams (1871) compiled and translated Chinese guest star and comet records based on *Wenxian Tongkao*, *Shi Ji*, *Qianhanshu* (History of the Former Han Dynasty), and other works.

Humboldt counted, screened, and surveyed 21 suspected novae in *Wenxian Tongkao* in his *Kosmos* (Humboldt, 1850).

Fotheringham (1919) investigated the reliability of the guest star and comet records of 134 BC and 120 BC and used these two records to examine the new star of Hipparchus and the dates of birth and accession of Mithridates.

Zinner (1919) compiled records of ancient Chinese guest star observations alongside contemporary nova observations and analyzed the consistency of novae with nebulae in position and spectrum.

Additionally, Lundmark referenced a translation of *Shi Ji* by the French sinologist É. Chavannes (1865–1918) and a compilation of ancient celestial records by E. B. Knobel (1841–1930) drawn from a translation of *Nihongi* by W. G. Aston (1841–1911) (Lundmark, 1921a).

For the names of the Chinese constellations and the conversion between the Chinese sexagenary cycle and the Gregorian calendar, Lundmark referred to the books of Biot and Williams. Biot (1846) referred to his father's article "On Ancient Chinese Astronomy," published in the *Journal des Savants* (Journal of Scholars), which provided an overview of Chinese astronomy and described the names, locations, and methods of dividing the celestial regions of China in 2357 BC and AD 1800. Williams (1871, pp. 15–38) referred to Biot's article along with John Reeves's (1774–1856) article "On Chinese Names of Stars and Constellations" and the Belgian Jesuit François Noël's (1651–1729) *Observationes Mathematicae et Physicae in India et China Fuctae* (Observations on Mathematics and Physics in India and China) for information on Chinese chronological conversions, celestial divisions, and the names of stars.

There are sixteen problematic records in Lundmark's survey of the pre-Tychonic novae, occurring in AD 64, 66, 70, 130, 185, 300, 389, 568, 827, 900, 945, 962, 1230, 1264, and 1461. Six representative cases are presented below as samples for analysis.

1. Suspected Nova Case in AD 64

Wenxian Tongkao records this entry as follows:

The third month of the 7th year of Yong Ping (May 3, 64). A guest star with two feet of luminous vapor, located south of Tai Wei's (Supreme Palace Enclosure) Left Zhi Fa (Left Law Administrator, a star on the wall of the Tai Wei / Supreme Palace Enclosure, in the region of Virgo), outside Duan Men (Gate of Correct Demeanor), was visible for 75 days. (Ma, 1994, p. 535)

Biot translated “with two feet of luminous vapor” as “La vapeur lumineuse embrassait 2 degrés” (The luminous vapor embraced 2 degrees). The expression “embrassait” (embraced) differs from “with two feet of luminous vapor” and is easily misinterpreted as suggesting that this object emitted light. The latter expression, by contrast, more closely describes the length of the guest star's tail.

Xi (1955) suggested that the description “with two feet of luminous vapor” indicates that this object was a comet. Lundmark judged the object to be a nova because it had not moved during 2.5 months and because Biot described it as an “étoile extraordinaire” (extraordinary star). However, many comets have long visible periods, the absence of a report of motion does not mean that the object was stationary, and the objects that Biot calls “étoile extraordinaire” include more than guest stars.

2. Suspected Nova Case in AD 66

For this case, Lundmark referred to the entry in Biot's translation of *Tongkao* and identified the object as a nova. *Tongkao* records this entry as follows:

On Wu Zi day, the twelfth month of the 8th year of Yong Ping of Emperor Xiao Ming (January 31, 66), a guest star appeared in the east. (Ma, 1994, p. 535)

Xi (1955) pointed out that:

Donghan Huiyao (Institutional History of the Eastern Han Dynasty) recorded the appearance of a comet: on Wu Shen day, the first month of the 9th year of Yong Ping (February 20, 66), a “guest star” came out from Qian Niu (Ox Star, a region that includes α Aquila), as long as 8 feet, passed Jian Xing (Establishment Star, around Sgr), and disappeared at the south of Fang (Room Star, β, δ, π, ν Sco). *The Gujinzhu of the Donghanshu* (Notes to Things Old and New of the Eastern Han Dynasty) recorded that this comet passed Dou (Dipper, $\mu, \lambda, \rho, \sigma, \tau, \zeta$ Sgr), Jian, Ji (Winnowing-basket), Fang, Jiao (Horn, ζ, θ, ι Vir and Spica), Kang (Neck, $\iota, \kappa, \lambda, \rho$ Vir), and arrived at Yi (Wings, 22 stars in Hya and Crt). Its flame pointed east and was visible for 50 days. Wu Shen day of the 1st month is February 20, only 20 days after January 31. At nine each night, the stars above are all in the east, so the nova seen there on January 31 could well have been the comet mentioned in the *Huiyao*. Moreover, the time of perihelion of Halley’s Comet was January 26 of that year, so this “nova” was probably Halley’s Comet.

3. Suspected Nova Case in AD 76

It is stated in the *Tianwenzhi* of the *Han Shu*:

The fourth month of the 5th year of Yuan Feng (May 76), a candle star was seen between Kui (the Legs, $\beta, \delta, \epsilon, \zeta, \eta, \mu, \nu, \pi$ And, and $\sigma_2, \tau, \nu, \phi, \chi, \psi$ Psc) and Lou (the Bond, α, β, γ Aries). (Ban, 1994, p. 86)

Lundmark referred to the translation by Williams (1871), who rendered “a candle star” as “a bright star.” However, the *Hanshu Tianwenzhi* contains the following explanation of the candle star:

The candle star looks like Venus; it appears without accompanying motion and is visible for a short time. Meng Kang said: “Three comets appear above this star, which is the essence of Saturn.”

According to this description, the brightness of this star was not low, but it may not have been visible for long. The statement “Three comets appear above this star, which is the essence of Saturn” suggests that the object was more likely associated with a comet or meteor than with a nova.

4. Spurious Supernova in AD 827

The Arabian astronomers Haly and Giafar observed a supernova at Babylon in 1006, which Humboldt tentatively dated to AD 827 (Stephenson, 1997):

The precise year (827) is doubtful. It may with more certainty be assigned to the first half of the ninth century, when in the reign of Caliph Al Mamoun, the two famous Arabian astronomers, Haly and Giafar Ben Mohammed Albumazar, observed at Babylon a new star whose light, according to their report, “equaled that of the moon in her quarters.” This natural phenomenon likewise occurred in Scorpio. The star disappeared after a period of four months. (*Kosmos*, trans. E. C. Otté, 1892, p. 212)

Lundmark included this star in his catalog, and it was subsequently included by Xi Zezong and Bo Shuren (1965). Tammann associated it with the radio source Sco X-3. However, according to Goldstein's investigation, this supernova is the same as SN 1006; the Arabic sources correspond to AD 1006, not AD 827 (Stephenson, 1997).

5. Suspected Nova Case in AD 900

It is stated in the *Tianwenzhi* of the *Xintangshu* (New Book of the Tang):

The first month of the 3rd year of Guang Hua (February 900), a guest star appeared at Huan Zhe (Eunuch Official) of Zhong Yuan (Middle Wall, including 60 Her, that is, the Tai Wei area, an area between Boö and Leo), as big as a peach. Its light shot at Huan Zhe, and Huan Zhe disappeared. (Liu, 1994, p. 739)

Biot translated "Its light shot at Huan Zhe, and Huan Zhe disappeared" as "Sa lumière effaçait le Groupe Houan-tche" (Its light erased the Huan Zhe group), which does not convey the sense that the light of the celestial body burst directly upon Huan Zhe. Here I agree with Chen Zungui's view that "Its light shot at Huan Zhe" indicates that this is a star with a tail.

6. Suspected Nova Case in AD 1618

In the morning of Bing Yin day, the eleventh month (December 9, 1618), a Hua Bai (grizzled) star can be seen in the east. (Zhang, 1994, p. 1453)

"Hua Bai" in Chinese means a gray-and-white mixture of colors (grizzled). Williams translated "Hua Bai" as "like a white flower," which is inaccurate. The *Ming Shilu*, to which Williams did not refer, records this phenomenon in greater detail:

On the morning of Xin You day of the tenth month (November 22), a star as big as a funnel emitted a thunder-like sound and fell beyond the Ander Gate in Nanjing, turning into a stone weighing twenty-one pounds. Wanshan village also reported two meteorite sightings, weighing one hundred and thirty pounds, both of which were stored in a warehouse in the capital. On Yi Chou day (November 26), a comet appeared from Di (Root), as big as an egg and several zhang's long (a zhang is a Chinese unit of measurement, equal to 3 1/3 meters), with a pale color and its tail pointing to the southeast. After ten days, the comet's tail turned to the northwest, swept past the star Taiyangshou (Guard of the Sun, χ UMa), and entered seven degrees and ten minutes into Kang (ι , κ , λ , ρ Vir). After another three days (December 9), the comet gradually traveled to the northwest. Its tail swept over the stars Tianxuan (Celestial Rotating Jade, β UMa) of the Northern Dipper, Tianji (Celestial Shining Pearl, γ UMa), Wenchang (Administrative Center, f UMa), and Wuche (Five Chariots, α , β , θ , ι Aur, and β Tau), and approached Ziyuan (the Purple Forbidden Enclosure, stars and constellations around the north pole), which was located at six degrees of Kang, and began to go out on the nineteenth day of the following month. That morning, another star with grizzled color was seen in the east, which appeared together with the comet. On Yi Si day of the eleventh month, a star fell from north to south, also as big as a funnel, making a sound like thunder. Its light shone on the earth and exploded into several pieces. (see Liu, 2019, p. 346)

“In the morning of Bing Yin day, the eleventh month, a grizzled star can be seen in the east” appears in the middle of this series of records in temporal terms. Combining the description in

the *Ming Shilu* with the fact that the star was seen in the east and was gray and white in color (and therefore not very bright), this is most likely a comet record or a record related to a fireball or meteorite rather than a nova.

Additionally, Biot, Zinner, Williams, and Lundmark did not include Chinese observations of SN 1572 in their catalogs. The historical record they consulted needs to be more comprehensive. The description of SN 1572 in the *Ming Shi* is relatively short:

There is a guest star next to Ce Xing (Whip Star, γ Cas), which just appeared in the first year of Wanli; it was large previously and now is small. (Zhang, 1994, p. 1425)

This record does not appear in *Ming Shi*, volume 27 (which focuses on guest stars and comets), but in volume 25 (which deals with fixed stars), and the detailed record of this star is preserved in the *Ming Shilu*:

On the third night of the tenth month (November 8), a guest star with a size like a bullet appeared next to Ge Dao (Flying Corridor, consisting of ϵ , δ , ι , ϕ , \omicron Cas, and a star among ν , ζ or even a little further south \omicron Cas) located in Bi Xiu (Net Mansion), gradually showing shimmery light. After nineteen days, on the night of Ren Shen (November 24), its color became ruddy yellow, its size became prominent as a lamp, and it grew radiant. Divination said it was a Bei Xing (star of calamity) ... from the second month of the first year of Wanli (February 1573), the light of this star became faint, and it disappeared in April of the second year of Wanli (February 1574). (see Liu, 2019, p. 322)

4.3 Lundmark's Organization and Investigation of Historical Stellar Luminosity Records

The organization of historical stellar luminosity records was one of Lundmark's primary projects from 1926 to 1932. This period coincided with the rapid development of stellar photometry, when techniques such as photometry and spectral analysis were increasingly applied to the study of stars, marking the transition of stellar astronomy into astrophysics.

Since the mid-19th century, significant progress had been made in both astrometry and astrophysics. By the early 20th century, American astronomer Henrietta Swan Leavitt had discovered a fixed relationship between the period of variability and the intrinsic brightness of Cepheid variables. This discovery enabled astronomers to use Cepheid variables as standard candles to determine the scale of the Milky Way. In the 1920s, Edwin Hubble and other astronomers used this method to demonstrate that the universe is expanding.

In 1905, Danish astronomer Ejnar Hertzsprung (1873–1967) was the first to reveal the relationship between stellar spectral types and luminosity. In 1911, he published a color-magnitude diagram for star clusters, while Russell independently discovered the giant star sequence and the dwarf star sequence in 1910 and published the first field star spectral-luminosity diagram in 1913. Since stellar color correlates with spectral type or surface temperature, both diagrams expressed the relationship between spectral type and luminosity. Together, Hertzsprung and Russell are credited with creating the Hertzsprung-Russell Diagram (H-R Diagram), which significantly advanced the theory of stellar evolution and provided a theoretical framework and tools for related studies.

During this period, astronomers also widely adopted astrophotography to measure stellar brightness. By comparing the brightness of stars across different photographic plates, they could analyze variations in stellar luminosity and gain a better understanding of the properties of variable stars.

Stellar Photometry and Lundmark's Work on Historical Stellar Luminosity Records

Stellar photometry focuses on the brightness and variability of stars and other celestial objects, helping to resolve questions about the nature of stars and galaxies. Lundmark believed that in this field, historical data are as important as modern observational results. He argued that both should be treated with equal significance and that the best approach was to organize scattered observational results from various astronomical documents in chronological order, using them as references for addressing specific problems (Lundmark, 1932a, p. 210).

Lundmark's contributions to the organization of stellar luminosity records are primarily reflected in four works:

The Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes by Ptolemaios, Al-Sufi, and Tycho Brahe (published in 1926);

On the Earliest Estimates of Stellar Sizes (published in 1927);

The Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes in the Star Catalog in K'in-Ting-I-Hsiang K'ao-Tch'eng (published in 1932); and

The chapter "Luminosities, Colours, Diameters, Densities, Masses of the Stars" in the *Handbuch der Astrophysik* (published in 1932).

In *The Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes by Ptolemaios, Al-Sufi, and Tycho Brahe*, Lundmark extended the investigations of astronomers such as E. C. Pickering (1846–1919) into the visual observations of stars by Ptolemy and Al-Sufi. Lundmark noted that Tycho Brahe’s star catalog had been largely overlooked with respect to its stellar magnitude records. He therefore decided to convert Tycho’s magnitudes into modern standardized values. Around the same time, Zinner conducted similar research, and his results were consistent with Lundmark’s expectations.

In this paper, Lundmark first reviewed the historical development of the concept of magnitudes and introduced the primary sources and the methods used to study them. He then examined historical data for 3,765 celestial objects (representing 1,239 distinct stars), including:

1,020 stars from Ptolemy’s star catalog;

1,014 stars from Al-Sufi’s catalog; and

773 and 958 stars from Tycho Brahe’s two catalogs, respectively.

Lundmark recorded the stellar magnitudes listed in these historical sources, the corresponding modern magnitude values, their mean values, the average errors, and the number of stars in each magnitude group, presenting them systematically in tables.

Ptolemaios (Pt)	1020 objects
Al Sûfi (AS)	1014 „
Tycho Brahe (B ₁)	773 „
„ „ (B ₂)	958 „
In total	1239 objects

.Old magn.	Ptolemaios (Pt)		Al Sûfi (AS)		Tycho Brahe (B ₁)		Tycho Brahe (B ₂)	
	Mean magn.	n						
1	0 ^m .52 ± 0 ^m .31	13	0 ^m .59 ± 0 ^m .33	13	0 ^m .39 ± 0 ^m .39	7	0 ^m .82 ± 0 ^m .30	12
1—2	1.55 0.65	2	1.05 0.13	2	1.40 0.36	5		
2—1	1.63 0.41	3	0.90 0.00	2				
2	2.21 0.13	34	1.88 0.08	25	2.31 0.08	29	2.17 0.10	41
2—3	2.93 0.26	7	2.44 0.11	7	2.27 0.27	7		
3—2	2.67 0.13	11	2.44 0.10	11	1.18 0.31	5		
3	3.28 0.05	175	2.93 0.06	95	3.37 0.06	99	3.44 0.05	159
3—4	3.81 0.17	21	3.54 0.04	93	3.60 0.11	34		
4—3	3.96 0.06	89	3.77 0.05	75	3.06 0.18	13		
4	4.35 0.03	362	4.26 0.03	265	4.21 0.04	187	4.25 0.03	329
4—5	4.76 0.13	18	4.53 0.05	86	4.32 0.06	54		
5—4	4.78 0.18	10	4.71 0.09	22	3.81 0.13	22		
5	4.91 0.04	204	4.72 0.03	166	4.68 0.04	122	4.75 0.03	232
5—6			5.11 0.06	67	4.87 0.13	27		
6—5					4.51 0.09	26		
6	5.29 0.05	50	5.25 0.04	70	5.22 0.04	100	5.24 0.04	180
6—7			5.65 0.08		5.20 0.11	20		
7—6					5.21 0.09	11		
neb	4.70 0.66	4	5.08 ± 0.70	4	5.80 ± 0.22	5	5.80 ± 0.23	5
αμ	4.76 ± 0.10	14						

Figure 4-4. Lundmark's organization and conversion of magnitude records in the Ptolemy, Al-Sufi, and Tycho catalogs.

Based on his investigation of historical data, Lundmark drew the following conclusions:

Non-uniform luminosity scales. The magnitude scales established by past observers were not evenly divided. The intervals between 4th and 6th magnitude stars were too small, while those between 2nd and 4th magnitude stars were too large. For celestial objects

with slightly brighter or dimmer colors (represented in tables as “1-2” or “2-1”), the variation in brightness does not directly correspond to an increase or decrease of 1/3 of a magnitude.

Consistency in high-weight data. In the sections with higher weights (those containing more stars), the values provided by the four star catalogs showed minimal discrepancies. This indicates that the most easily determined magnitudes in these historical records exhibit a consistent systematic error. Therefore, Al-Sufi’s magnitude data were likely revisions of Ptolemy’s original records.

Agreement at the lowest magnitudes. Tycho Brahe’s data do not overlap with those of his predecessors, but the values for the lowest magnitudes are remarkably similar, a point that Lundmark found noteworthy.

Following these analyses, Lundmark attempted to estimate the potential systematic errors in individual observations. He proposed that the systematic error Δm could be derived using a formula in which T represents the date of the star catalog. He then presented the potential error values derived from his analysis.

	Prob. error of one observation	Mean difference. Old magn. — Harvard
Ptolemaios	$\pm 0^m.37$	$- 0^m.18$
Al Sûfi	± 0.30	$+ 0.02$
Tycho Brahe (B ₁)	± 0.36	$+ 0.18$
” ” (B ₂)	± 0.37	$+ 0.04$

$$\Delta m = \pm 0^m.1272 \pm 0^m.000146 (1900 - T)$$

$$\pm 0.0980 \pm 0.000076$$

Figure 4-5. Lundmark's example of systematic error in a single observation and its derivation.

Lundmark believed that these records reflected minor changes in stellar brightness (though stellar brightness does not vary by more than one magnitude over 10,000 years). He also suggested that, with access to a sufficiently large number of stellar catalogs and assuming that their systematic errors follow a Gaussian distribution, this formula could provide an unbiased measure of long-term changes in stellar luminosity.

According to Lundmark, there are two possible causes for variations in stellar luminosity:

Changes in the distance between the Sun and the stars; and

Actual changes in the stars' intrinsic luminosity.

With more data, it would be possible to better determine whether long-term variations in stellar luminosity truly exist and to understand their underlying causes.

Table IV.

Colour index	Colour equations							
	Pt	<i>n</i>	AS	<i>n</i>	B ₁	<i>n</i>	B ₂	<i>n</i>
— 0 ^m .4 to — 0 ^m .2	+ 0 ^m .16	163	+ 0 ^m .10	162	+ 0 ^m .03	114	— 0 ^m .01	137
— 0.1 „ + 0.2	— 0.06	368	— 0.09	364	0 00	295	+ 0 02	354
+ 0.3 „ + 0.5	+ 0.04	103	+ 0.03	101	— 0 05	79	0 00	100
+ 0.6 „ + 0.8	+ 0.08	80	+ 0.10	82	+ 0.01	58	— 0.02	75
+ 0.9 „ + 1.4	— 0.01	269	0.00	264	— 0.06	201	— 0 04	252
+ 1.5 „ + 1.8	— 0.01	35	+ 0 06	35	+ 0.23	26	+ 0.22	34

Figure 4-6. Lundmark's grouping of residuals from historical observations based on color indices.

Lundmark also sought to address another question using these data: whether human sensitivity to light of different colors has changed over time. He grouped residuals derived after applying systematic errors to ancient magnitude records based on the color indices shown in the figure. According to his findings, there have been no significant changes in human sensitivity to light of different colors or in the inherent colors of stars over the centuries.

In the 1927 paper *On the Earliest Estimates of Stellar Sizes*, Lundmark supplemented his 1926 research. He proposed that stellar magnitudes are unrelated to a star's actual size or dimensions and are instead a classification based solely on brightness. He explained that the human eye responds logarithmically to observed light intensity, so that when light intensity increases geometrically, the perception of brightness increases only arithmetically. This concept underpins the magnitude system used for stars.

Lundmark believed that these observational records could help researchers determine whether and to what extent stellar brightness changes over time. His investigation was based on the following hypotheses:

Ancient and modern observers might perceive colors differently. By comparing ancient and modern observations of stellar brightness, it is possible to identify any systematic differences in their perceptions.

Comparing the earliest photometric data with modern measurements allows for an analysis of their accuracy and supports valuable conclusions.

Storleksklass.	Intensitet.	Logaritmen för intensiteterna.
1.....	1	0.00
2.....	1/2.512	— 0.40
3.....	1/6.310	— 0.80
4.....	1/15.849	— 1.20
5.....	1/39.811	— 1.60
6.....	1/100.000	— 2.00

Figure 4-7. Lundmark's display of stars on a logarithmic scale at intervals of 0.40.

Lundmark extracted magnitude estimates for stars made by Tycho Brahe, Ptolemy, and Al-Sufi and compared them to brightness measurements from the Harvard Photometry Catalog. Before Lundmark, no one had conducted such a comparison.

Lundmark then demonstrated the relationship between modern photometric measurements and the earliest magnitude estimates. He also provided a graph showing the relationship between residual observational errors and stellar color. Based on his analysis, Lundmark concluded that:

The luminosity scales in the three star catalogs (Ptolemy, Al-Sufi, and Tycho Brahe) are relatively consistent in their baseline and overall trends.

The photometric measurements by Ptolemy and Al-Sufi align to some extent, but Tycho Brahe's scale may differ slightly from the other two, possibly because of different observational methods or materials.

Examining the magnitudes recorded in these catalogs further, Lundmark suggested that stellar brightness might decrease by one magnitude over 10,000 years, although the actual

change is likely much smaller. Such changes could result from stellar motion or intrinsic luminosity variations, but both would be minimal.

Based on the relationship between residual observational errors and stellar color, Lundmark concluded that stellar colors had not changed over the 2,000 years covered by the photometric observations. He also refuted the idea that ancient observers perceived stellar colors differently from modern observers.

Figure 4-8. Comparison of Lundmark's magnitude estimates from Tycho, Ptolemy, and Al-Sufi with the photometric measurements in the Harvard Revised Photometry catalog.

In his 1932 paper *The Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes in the Star Catalog in K'in-Ting-I-Hsiang K'ao-Tch'eng*, Lundmark addressed the same questions as in his 1926 and 1927 studies: deriving stellar color equations from historical data and establishing a foundation for 18th-century stellar magnitudes to support research into the long-term variability of stellar brightness.

Lundmark investigated the contents of the *Qianlong Star Catalog* and concluded that its magnitude data, expressed as integers, were relatively crude. In terms of precision, the brightness estimates in the *Qianlong Star Catalog* were less accurate than those in Ptolemy's catalog and significantly less precise than Al-Sufi's estimates, with average errors of ± 0.745 mag and ± 0.34 mag, respectively.

Despite its crudeness, Lundmark considered the *Qianlong Star Catalog*, created in the record-scarce 18th century, an important source. Converting its content into Harvard Revised Photometry (HRP) values was a crucial task that could provide additional material for studying stellar evolution. He also believed the existing scale was sufficient to infer the proper motion of stars.

In this investigation, Lundmark converted the magnitudes of 1,272 stars from the *Qianlong Star Catalog* based on spectral and magnitude data provided in the Draper Catalog. He grouped stars by spectral type and magnitude, calculated average errors, and plotted the results. Using these data, he derived stellar color equations.

Spectral Class	Chinese Catalogue		1 ^m		2 ^m		3 ^m		4 ^m		5 ^m		6 ^m	
		N		N		N		N		N		N		N
Oa-B3	—	—	1 ^m 926 ± 0 ^m 158	16	3 ^m 079 ± 0 ^m 140	29	4 ^m 062 ± 0 ^m 093	59	4 ^m 719 ± 0 ^m 070	55	5 ^m 305 ± 0 ^m 057	70		
B5-B9	0 ^m 872 ± 0 ^m 240	4	2.372 ± 0.184	5	3.638 ± 0.120	19	4.421 ± 0.077	42	4.885 ± 0.080	82	5.616 ± 0.045	116		
A0-A5	0.242 ± 0.495	5	2.307 ± 0.097	21	3.515 ± 0.109	47	4.352 ± 0.058	110	4.954 ± 0.049	165	5.680 ± 0.032	345		
F0-F8	—	—	2.058 ± 0.060	5	3.675 ± 0.126	27	4.213 ± 0.074	58	5.082 ± 0.069	91	5.842 ± 0.048	183		
G0-G8	0.402 ± 0.176	4	—	—	3.344 ± 0.146	22	4.459 ± 0.089	38	4.973 ± 0.080	59	5.704 ± 0.046	152		
K0-K2	—	—	2.198 ± 0.150	9	3.468 ± 0.081	47	4.225 ± 0.054	102	4.896 ± 0.049	150	5.739 ± 0.036	305		
K5-Ma	1.052 ± 0.341	4	2.514 ± 0.209	8	3.466 ± 0.165	13	4.249 ± 0.114	35	5.014 ± 0.075	55	5.679 ± 0.063	101		
All Classes	0.518 ± 0.196	17	2.208 ± 0.093	64	3.456 ± 0.047	204	4.274 ± 0.017	444	4.937 ± 0.024	657	5.694 ± 0.017	1271		

Figure 4-9. Lundmark's grouping of the 1,272 stars in the «Qianlong Star Catalog» by spectral type and magnitude.

Figure 4-10. Lundmark's color equations for the contents of the «Qianlong Star Catalog».

Lundmark concluded that, despite significant uncertainties, color equations should be treated as a function of apparent magnitude. The color equation changes gradually from bright to faint stars, possibly because of the Gallissot Effect. However, as the curve is nonlinear, more data are needed to support this conclusion.

Lundmark's final work in this field was the chapter "Luminosities, Colours, Diameters, Densities, Masses of the Stars" in Volume IV of the *Handbuch der Astrophysik*. This handbook, a classic reference in astrophysics, was collaboratively written by 33 authors from around the world, who could choose to write in English or German. It compiled extensive observational data and showcased cutting-edge research in the rapidly developing astrophysics field of the 1930s, filling gaps in related studies, proposing new questions, and providing a valuable resource for future researchers. The handbook remains a widely cited reference for astronomers (Stratton, 1934).

In his chapter, Lundmark took a historical perspective, organizing research on stellar properties such as luminosity and color. Unlike his earlier work, which aimed to address specific questions

(e.g., long-term changes in stellar color and brightness), this chapter was intended as a reference for researchers, with a broader scope and focus.

Lundmark noted that issues such as long-term variability in stellar luminosity depend entirely on direct observational results, as purely theoretical astrophysics cannot contribute to such questions. These issues span long timescales, and Lundmark regarded ancient and modern observations as equally valuable data sources. He argued that categorizing them as “ancient” or “modern” was impractical, emphasizing that the best approach to explaining and addressing issues related to stellar color, mass, density, and size was to organize the data chronologically (Lundmark, 1932a).

In the chapter, Lundmark introduced the history of stellar observations in chronological order, covering Scandinavia, Hipparchus, Ptolemy, ancient Babylon, Egypt, and China. He analyzed magnitude records in different historical materials, comparing them with modern catalogs such as the Bonner Durchmusterung (BD), Henry Draper Catalog (HD), and Harvard Revised Photometry (HRP). Lundmark also discussed the precision of these materials, the relationship between stellar magnitudes and colors, and the correlation between the number of stars and their apparent magnitudes.

Regarding Chinese observations of stellar brightness, Lundmark commented:

The oldest observational records from the civilized era come from China, and we have proven their high value, which has expanded our knowledge. Chinese records of comets and novae date back a long time, but they seem to have preserved no observations of ordinary stellar magnitudes, nor did they even roughly classify stars by brightness. In the 7th-century work *Star Guide Song*,

Dan Yuanzi described 283 constellations containing 1,464 stars. However, the star charts from that period displayed slightly fewer stars and failed to distinguish between magnitudes. (Lundmark, 1932a, p. 221)

4.4 Conclusion

The development of historical astronomy is closely tied to the overall progress of astronomy, a relationship demonstrated in Chapters 2 and 3. Lundmark's attention to ancient records reflected both his personal interests and the specific questions arising in his research, a connection that becomes even more evident in this chapter. Through the investigation of his organization of ancient guest star records and historical stellar luminosity records, it is clear that historical records served as an essential source of data for Lundmark and for later researchers.

Lundmark's specific work makes clear that the questions he pursued were closely tied to the broader concerns of astronomy in his time. His organization of ancient guest star records and historical stellar luminosity records contributed to problems of stellar and cosmic evolution, issues that engaged both his personal interest and the wider astronomical community of his era.

Lundmark believed that historical astronomical records could effectively compensate for the limited temporal range of modern observational data, and for this reason he regarded them as irreplaceably significant.

This chapter highlights two of Lundmark's major contributions to the organization of historical astronomical records, which together reflect his research approach: selection and investigation, data conversion, and problem solving. In his study of ancient guest star records, Lundmark first examined the reliability of the observational data. He then identified celestial phenomena, most

likely novae, from ancient Chinese guest star records. After investigating the specific event dates and galactic coordinates, he compiled the information into tables for his own use and for future researchers.

Similarly, in his study of historical stellar magnitudes, Lundmark first analyzed the precision of the records. He then converted them into numerical values corresponding to modern magnitudes and used them to investigate specific questions, such as whether stellar luminosity or color had changed significantly over long periods. His work in this area also provided valuable insights for later researchers.

The following chapter focuses on Lundmark's use of historical records to address problems related to stellar and cosmic evolution. Through case studies, it demonstrates the value of historical records in astronomical research and illustrates the relationship between historical astronomy and the development of modern astronomy. It also addresses two key questions: how reliable were Lundmark's efforts to organize historical astronomical records as a supplement to observational data, and what inspiration did his research provide to later scholars? These questions are explored in greater detail in the chapters that follow.

Chapter 5: Lundmark's Use of Ancient Astronomical Records to Address Celestial Evolution Problems

The preceding chapters analyzed Lundmark's efforts to organize ancient astronomical records and described the content of his research. These efforts provided strong support for solving many problems in astronomy. Through his collation and selection of ancient nova records, Lundmark identified consistencies in the distribution of novae and celestial objects such as nebulae. The historical records supported his understanding of the nature of nebulae, his measurement of cosmic scales, and his analysis of nova evolution. Historical records of stellar luminosity also aided his study of stellar evolution.

Lundmark's work on celestial evolution is one of the most representative examples of his use of ancient astronomical records, and it offers significant insights for addressing similar problems in astronomy. The sections that follow focus on this area of his research. Through case studies, this chapter examines his use of ancient guest star records to study novae, the nature of nebulae, and the measurement of galactic scales, as well as his use of historical stellar luminosity records to study stellar evolution. By analyzing his methods, the chapter aims to show how ancient astronomical records can be applied to modern astronomical problems and to provide a foundation for further exploration of their value in modern astronomy.

5.1 Lundmark's Conclusions on Novae and the Nature of Nebulae Based on Ancient Guest Star Records

Between July 1921 and April 1923, Lundmark conducted nine studies on the nature of novae. These studies addressed a range of topics, including the distribution patterns, luminosity, and

eruption frequency of novae. His paper *Suspected New Stars Recorded in Old Chronicles and Among Recent Meridian Observations* belongs to this series. Tables 5-1a and 5-1b summarize the nine studies.

Table 5-1a. Lundmark's studies on novae (Part 1).

Table 5-1a: Lundmark's Studies on Novae (Part 1)

Date	Title	Summary	Source
July 15, 1921	<i>The Apparent Distribution of the Novae</i>	Points out that nova distribution is not proportional to stellar density and may relate to dark nebulae. Introduces a series of papers on nova research.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i> , Vol. 33, No. 194, pp. 219–220
July 16, 1921	<i>Suspected New Stars Recorded in Old Chronicles and Among Recent Meridian Observations</i>	Investigates and selects ancient East Asian guest star records, summarizes brightness information, and finds novae clustered near the Galactic center.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i> , Vol. 33, No. 195, pp. 225–238
November 10, 1921	<i>Notes From Pacific Coast Observations Nova Aquilae No. 4</i>	Introduces Nova Aquilae No. 4, noting its position in the Milky Way's dark lane. Suggests novae relate to nebular material rather than stellar density.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i> , Vol. 33, No. 196, pp. 314–316
December 1921	<i>The Spiral Nebula Messier 33</i>	Examines the structure, spectrum, and potential distance of Messier 33, suggesting it consists of ordinary stars, star clusters, and nebular material.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i> , Vol. 33, No. 196, pp. 324–327
January 1922	<i>The Distribution of Novae</i>	Explores nova distribution, luminosity, spectrum, and relationships with other stellar types. Notes associations with dark nebulae rather than density.	<i>Publications of the American Astronomical Society</i> , Vol. 4, pp. 368–370

Table 5-1b. Lundmark's studies on novae (Part 2).

Table 5-1b: Lundmark's Studies on Novae (Part 2)

Date	Title	Summary	Source
March 15, 1922	<i>Father Hagen's Papers on Dark Nebulae</i>	Introduces Father Hagen's research, suggesting the Milky Way's surroundings are covered with dark nebulae. Recommends repeated observations for verification.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i> , Vol. 34, No. 200, pp. 191–199
August 19, 1922	<i>The Absolute Magnitudes of Novae</i>	Discusses nova distribution linked to dark nebulae, not uniformly along Galactic longitude, and hints at connections to distant Galactic regions.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i> , Vol. 34, No. 200, pp. 207–211
October 1922	<i>Nova Z Centauri (1896) and N.G.C.5253, with Edwin P. Hubble</i>	Collaborates with Hubble to observe this spiral galaxy, finding stellar characteristics similar to G-type stars.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i> , Vol. 34, No. 201, pp. 292–293
February 28, 1923	<i>Some Facts and Suggestions Concerning Nova</i>	Cites ancient nova records to show clustering in Cygnus and Aquila regions. Adjusted weightings suggest further clustering near $\lambda_0=337^\circ$.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i> , Vol. 35, No. 204, pp. 95–117

Key Findings from Lundmark's Studies

Distribution of Novae

Lundmark (1921c), using Pickering's 18-hour Galactic region map and Graff's 6-hour region intensity curves, highlighted that novae are more commonly found in regions with lower luminosity than in areas with higher stellar density. He observed a correlation between nova occurrence and the distribution of bright and dark nebulae.

Lundmark proposed that novae, given their proximity to nebulae, might be typical galactic objects related to nebular material. By assuming that the average distance of novae was similar to that of globular clusters, he estimated the average parallax of novae using values provided by

Shapley and other researchers. This led him to conclude that the absolute magnitude of novae at their peak brightness is exceptionally high, averaging around -9 magnitude (Lundmark, 1921c).

Lundmark also noted the similarity in distribution between planetary nebulae and novae. He posited that planetary nebulae could originate from novae, given the average brightness difference of about 10 magnitudes between their maximum and minimum luminosity (Lundmark, 1921b).

Novae Evolution

In the second part of *Suspected New Stars Recorded in Old Chronicles*, Lundmark reiterated his hypothesis that planetary nebulae may result from novae (Lundmark, 1921b). This idea also appeared in *Notes from Pacific Coast Observations: Nova Aquilae No. 4* (Lundmark, 1921a), where he emphasized:

Many observed instances support the view that novae are associated with nebular material in the universe. They appear in the Milky Way not because of the region's high stellar density but because of the irregular bright and dark nebulae typical of the galactic environment.

In *The Absolute Magnitudes of Novae*, Lundmark further noted:

Novae do not distribute uniformly along the galactic longitude. Instead, many appear associated with the distant center of our Milky Way. Based on Shapley's work, the galactic center's distance is estimated at 20,000 parsecs. Assuming that novae in the Sagittarius–Scorpius region share this average distance, their mean absolute magnitude is calculated to be -9 . (Lundmark, 1922)

Clustering of Novae

In *Some Facts and Suggestions Concerning Nova*, Lundmark analyzed clustering patterns in nova distribution:

Visibly observable novae cluster in the Cygnus and Aquila regions. Ancient records show these celestial events concentrate around $\lambda_0 = 384^\circ$. When adjusted for actual conditions and weighted, the concentration shifts to $\lambda_0 = 337^\circ$.

(Lundmark, 1923)

Summary of Lundmark's Conclusions

Distribution. Both ancient and modern records indicate that novae cluster toward the galactic center. This distribution is unrelated to stellar density but correlates with bright and dark irregular nebulae. According to Lundmark's calculations, observable novae concentrate near Cygnus and Aquila, while ancient novae cluster around $\lambda_0 = 384^\circ$ (unweighted) or $\lambda_0 = 337^\circ$ (weighted). It should be noted that galactic longitude is conventionally measured over the range 0° – 360° , so the figure $\lambda_0 = 384^\circ$ reported here lies outside the standard range (being equivalent to 24°) and should be read with caution; it recurs in several of Lundmark's distance arguments below.

Evolution. Lundmark identified a connection between novae and nebulae, proposing that novae originate from giant and dwarf stars and represent a stage in stellar evolution. He suggested that planetary nebulae may result from novae because of their similar distribution and brightness differences.

Luminosity. Novae exhibit a peak absolute magnitude of -9 , while planetary nebulae have an average brightness of about 0 magnitude. The 10-magnitude difference between

their maximum and minimum luminosity supports the hypothesis of a shared evolutionary relationship.

Contribution of Ancient Records

Ancient nova records provided additional observational data that supplemented modern findings. These records enabled Lundmark to analyze nova evolution comprehensively, linking their distribution and luminosity to nebulae and advancing the hypothesis that novae evolve into planetary nebulae.

5.2 Using Ancient Guest Star Records to Measure Galactic Scales

In 1943, Lundmark discussed the foundations of measuring cosmic scales in his historical work on astronomy, *Nya himlar*:

Problemet om bestämningen av astronomiens jätteavstånd bygger direkt på bestämningarna av astronomiska avstånd överhuvud. Dessa i sin tur basera sig på de direkta distansuppmätningarna och deras utvidgning i form av mätningar eller taxeringar av den absoluta ljusmängden. Vid en återblick på de grundvalar på vilka våra största avstånd bygga, blir det nödvändigt att åtminstone antyda den fascinerande historien om hur avståndsbestämningarna inom astronomin så småningom ha blivit möjliga och hur uppmätningen av himlakropparnas ljusmängd (fotometri) och analysen av ljuset (spektralanalysen) samt sist men icke minst, den fotografiska avbildningen av himlakropparna ha kunnat förverkligas.

(The problem of determining the giant distances of astronomy rests directly upon the determination of astronomical distances in general. These, in turn, are based on the direct measurements of distance and on their extension in the form of measurements or estimates of the absolute amount of light. In looking back at the foundations on which our largest distances rest, it becomes necessary to indicate at least something of the fascinating history of how the determination of distances in astronomy gradually became possible — and how the measurement of the celestial bodies' amount of light (photometry), the analysis of that light (spectral analysis), and, last but not least, the photographic recording of the celestial bodies came to be realized.)

As early as 1919, in his doctoral dissertation, Lundmark hypothesized that novae in the Andromeda Galaxy were similar to those in the Milky Way. By investigating the absolute magnitudes of novae within the Milky Way and comparing them with those observed in Andromeda, he cautiously concluded that the distance between the two galaxies was approximately 600,000 light-years.

In 1920, supported by the Sweden-America Foundation, Lundmark worked at the Mount Wilson Observatory and Lick Observatory in the United States. As one of the staunchest proponents of the island universe theory, he sought more evidence that spiral nebulae were located outside the Milky Way. This theory was consolidated when Edwin Hubble discovered Cepheid variables in 1924 and calculated the distances to M31 and M33 as 930,000 light-years and to NGC 6822 as 700,000 light-years in 1925.

Lundmark's research on galactic scales, spanning the years 1920 to 1927, recognized the value of ancient guest star records. In 1922, in *The Absolute Magnitudes of Novae*, Lundmark noted:

It seems that novae are associated with the dark nebulae in our stellar system, as indicated in my previous works published in Vol. 33 of this journal on pages 219, 225, and 314 in 1921. Attempts to deduce parallaxes for many dark nebulae suggest that they are located hundreds or even thousands of light-years away.

In 1923, in *Some Facts and Suggestions Concerning Nova*, Lundmark reiterated this point in greater detail:

I have previously noted in several papers that the distribution of novae indicates a connection with bright and dark nebular objects. This was initially identified by comparing the structure of the Milky Way with nova locations. Novae appear in regions with lower stellar density or at the edges of galactic nebulae. So far, the evidence suggests a relationship between novae and nebular matter. (Lundmark, 1923)

Lundmark then attempted to estimate the average distances of novae in the Milky Way by correlating them with the parallaxes of dark and bright nebulae:

The association of dark nebulae with novae provides another indication of the average distances to galactic novae. Previous studies have derived approximate parallaxes for dark and bright nebulae, with distances ranging from 150 to 15,000 light-years (excluding two particularly distant cases). The average distance of galactic nebulae is about 3,000 light-years. By comparing nebulae and novae, we

can infer the average distance to the latter. This comparison suggests that novae are typically located far from us. Data from ancient records also indicate that visible novae cluster in the $\lambda_0 = 384^\circ$ region. After weighting these observations, this clustering shifts to $\lambda_0 = 337^\circ$. (Lundmark, 1923)

He further stated:

Assuming that novae in the galaxy are associated with the nebulae in Sagittarius and Scorpius, we can use Shapley's estimates to determine that the average magnitude of the 16 novae observed in Sagittarius is -9.5 . (Lundmark, 1923)

Lundmark used these findings to argue that novae were closely related to dark and bright nebulae, and he calculated their average absolute magnitude as -9.5 .

In his 1925 paper, *The Motions and Distances of Spiral Nebulae*, Lundmark summarized his findings in support of the island universe theory (Lundmark, 1925). His 1927 work, *Studies of Anagalactic Nebulae*, built on these conclusions (Lundmark, 1927b).

In the 1925 paper, Lundmark explained how he determined that novae in spiral galaxies and in the Milky Way were similar types of celestial bodies. He hypothesized that novae in the Milky Way and Andromeda shared a similar apparent distribution within their respective galaxies, concentrating near the galactic center. This similarity indicated a relationship between the two galaxies. Moreover, the independent appearance of novae in Andromeda supported the conclusion that it was an independent galaxy:

There is ample evidence to suggest that novae are not new stars but originate from ordinary stars of various categories. Continuous observations of the Andromeda

Nebula might reveal ten or more novae annually. Considering the timescale of astronomical phenomena, the number of nova eruptions in the nebula must be immense. Although repeated nova stages for the same star are possible, they remain exceedingly rare. Thus, it is reasonable to hypothesize that the Andromeda Nebula is a massive stellar system containing millions of stars. (Lundmark, 1925)

In 1927, Lundmark further analyzed his findings, comparing them with contemporary astronomical results. Discussing nova luminosity, distances, and distribution, he proposed using nova clustering and inclination angles to calculate distances. Using the data from the Suspected Nova Table for 47 novae, Lundmark derived a clustering at right ascension 217° and declination $+60^\circ$. He acknowledged, however, that observational uncertainties limited precision.

Lundmark also referenced 56 post-1572 novae, recalculating their clustering at right ascension 186° , declination $+38^\circ.8$, and inclination $-3^\circ.9$. Excluding six uncertain cases, he found that the remaining novae concentrated at right ascension $18^\circ.7$, declination $+34^\circ.7$, with inclination $-2^\circ.6$, closely matching O-type stars and planetary nebulae. He calculated their distance as 35 parsecs and their average absolute magnitude as 3.5. Using 92 Cepheid variables in the Milky Way with periods over one day, he determined their distance as 97.8 parsecs and their absolute magnitude as 5.9 (Lundmark, 1927b). Taken at face value these figures are difficult to credit: a distance of only 35 parsecs and a mean absolute magnitude of about +3.5 are far too small and too faint for novae, objects for which Lundmark elsewhere derived $M \approx -9$, while a value of +5.9 is likewise implausible for Cepheids. The anomaly is itself instructive, for it exposes the limits of deriving distances from the apparent clustering of novae—a procedure that depends on the assumption of a common distance and whose large uncertainty Lundmark himself acknowledged, treating it as far less secure than the Cepheid distance scale.

Although Lundmark's approach to estimating intergalactic distances using nova clustering in Sagittarius was imprecise compared with methods involving Cepheid variables, his work demonstrated the critical role of ancient records in astronomical research.

Ancient East Asian guest star records provided Lundmark with additional observational data on novae and supernovae, including information on appearance frequency, apparent magnitude, and spatial relationships. Combined with spectral studies, these records highlighted the connections between novae and nebulae, aiding Lundmark in his efforts to measure cosmic scales. Covering a broader timeframe, these records also offered valuable evidence for Lundmark and his contemporaries as they traced the evolutionary processes of novae.

5.3 Using Ancient Guest Star Records to Study the Evolution of Novae and Supernovae

Ancient guest star records played a significant role in Lundmark's research into the evolution of novae and supernovae. While using novae as a scale to measure intergalactic distances, Lundmark encountered a challenging problem: some novae were extraordinarily bright (for example, Nova S Andromedae of 1885, which reached one-tenth the brightness of the entire Andromeda Galaxy). This contradicted the hypothesis of the island universe theory, which posited that Andromeda comprised millions of stars. To address this, Lundmark classified novae into "upper" and "lower" categories, hypothesizing that the two represented distinct phenomena (Kärnfelt, 2009, p. 145).

Historical records provided Lundmark with additional examples of "upper" novae. In 1932, in *The Pre-Tychonic Novae*, he referred to pre-1572 nova records as pre-Tychonic novae. In this paper, Lundmark examined the distribution and average absolute magnitudes of suspected novae

in Chinese records and concluded that these historical guest stars predominantly represented “upper” novae, or “supernovae.” It is worth clarifying the often-repeated claim that Lundmark coined the term “supernova” here. The word is generally credited to Walter Baade and Fritz Zwicky, who introduced “super-novae” in seminars at Caltech around 1931; Lundmark was, however, apparently the first to put it into print (as “super-Novae,” in a paper dated December 31, 1932 and published in 1933). In the present 1932 study he still used the description “upper-class” novae rather than the term itself.

In this paper, Lundmark reviewed studies of the distribution of pre-Tychonic novae and found that, like post-1572 novae, they concentrated in the Sagittarius–Scorpius region. He emphasized that these objects were unlikely to be comets or planets. Using the least-squares method, he calculated their concentration point in galactic longitude as $\lambda_0 = 384^\circ$. He concluded:

Given that these objects are concentrated in the central region of the Milky Way, it is reasonable to estimate the distance to this region as 26,000 light-years.

Conservatively assuming the maximum apparent magnitude of these objects as 1, their absolute magnitude would be $\bar{M}_{\max} = -13.5$. This result firmly places them in the “upper-class” category, or as supernovae.

Lundmark also estimated the supernova explosion frequency: approximately one per century in the Milky Way and one every 60 years in extragalactic systems (Lundmark, 1932c).

The Crab Nebula and Supernovae

The advent of astrophotography revolutionized the study of nebulae. In 1937, Mayall used the Crossley reflector to obtain the overall spectrum of the Crab Nebula. Through spectral analysis,

Mayall (1937) discovered that the nebula was expanding and that its spectral lines closely resembled those observed by Humason around Nova Persei 2. This finding led Mayall to revisit the idea that the Crab Nebula might be the remnant of an ancient nova.

In his paper, Mayall referenced Lundmark's footnote in *Suspected New Stars*, which had highlighted the positional correlation between the 1054 supernova and NGC 1952 (the Crab Nebula). Using Hubble's calculations, Mayall concluded that the nebula would have required approximately 900 years to expand to its current size, aligning closely with the Chinese observations of the 1054 supernova (Mayall, 1937).

In 1938, prompted by Mayall's research, Lundmark published *Was the Crab Nebula Formed by a Supernova in 1054 A.D.?* This study relied on two primary sources: ancient Chinese and Japanese guest star records and contemporary research on the physical properties and internal motion of the Crab Nebula. Lundmark aimed to demonstrate that the Crab Nebula was the remnant of a medieval nova, most likely a supernova (Lundmark, 1938).

Verifying the 1054 Supernova

At the start of his paper, Lundmark reviewed earlier research on ancient guest star records, including his own findings. He incorporated new material from Japanese astronomer Yasuaki Iba, who had translated approximately nine potential pre-Tychonic nova cases. Iba, an amateur astronomer, introduced foreign audiences to Shigeru Kanda's compilation of ancient Japanese astronomical records, *Historical Astronomical Materials of Japan*. Among these records was a description of the 1054 supernova:

In the second year of Tiansi, mid-April, during the Chou hour, a guest star appeared near the fourth star of Taurus, visible in the east. It was as large as Jupiter. (Iba, 1934)

Lundmark acknowledged the limitations of such historical observations:

Such observations were approximate. Equating this star to Jupiter likely underestimates its magnitude. Based on historical materials and the estimations of these untrained observers, it is evident that this bright star's magnitude was underestimated. While Chinese and Japanese observers were likely well trained, they certainly did not establish a photometric scale. (Lundmark, 1938)

Lundmark valued the reliability of Chinese records, stating:

Several cases from China have been well documented, reminding us that Japanese observations also merit high regard. However, history teaches us that everything is subject to scrutiny, and nearly all historical information has been or will be questioned. Nonetheless, Chinese observations have repeatedly verified occurrences of Halley's Comet. Moreover, records from China and Japan independently confirm the appearances of Tycho's 1572 nova and Kepler's 1604 nova, with some corroboration from Western sources.

Using historical and spectral data, Lundmark recalculated the maximum apparent magnitude of the 1054 supernova as $\bar{M}_{\max} = -13.2$. While acknowledging potential underestimation in the absence of a photometric scale, he concluded that this object was undoubtedly a supernova.

Relying on Mayall's calculations, Lundmark determined that the interval between the supernova's explosion and 1938 was 808 ± 73 years, pinpointing the explosion to around AD 1105 ± 73 (Lundmark, 1938).

Impact and Legacy

By incorporating Japanese records, Lundmark corroborated details about the timing and location of the 1054 supernova. The brightness descriptions in these records further confirmed the object as a supernova. His research sparked interest in the Crab Nebula and led to further investigations by Oort, Duyvendak, and others into Chinese records of the 1054 supernova. These studies established the Crab Nebula as one of the brightest supernovae observed in recorded history.

With the rise of radio astronomy, the uniqueness of the Crab Nebula became even more apparent, as it was identified as one of the first radio sources. This discovery spurred investigations into the relationship between radio sources and supernova explosions. Given the rarity of supernovae in the Milky Way, the astronomical community increasingly turned to ancient astronomical records, advancing historical astronomy as a field.

5.4 Using Ancient Stellar Luminosity Records to Study Stellar Evolution

The relationship between stellar luminosity changes and stellar evolution is closely interconnected. Lundmark sought to understand the physical properties of stars by observing changes in their luminosity, thereby determining their evolutionary stages. He paid attention to historical records of stellar luminosity changes, believing that comparing modern and ancient measurements could reveal whether stellar luminosity had generally decreased, increased, or remained stable over time. He viewed ancient observational records as critically important

(Lundmark, 1943, p. 215). Through a series of investigations, Lundmark concluded that changes in stellar luminosity were minimal, indicating a very slow evolutionary process for stars.

In two articles published in 1926 and 1927, *The Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes by Ptolemaios, Al-Sufi, and Tycho Brahe* and *On the Earliest Estimates of Stellar Sizes*, Lundmark studied the luminosity estimates of stars by ancient astronomers such as Ptolemy, Al-Sufi, and the Renaissance-era Tycho Brahe. He concluded that stellar luminosity had changed very little over time and that neither human visual perception nor the colors of stars had significantly altered since ancient times (Lundmark, 1926; Lundmark, 1927a).

Lundmark (1928) requested data from Zinner regarding his catalog of stellar luminosities and received a reply in which Zinner shared his findings (E. Zinner, personal communication, July 23, 1928).

In 1932, Lundmark published *Secular Change in Stellar Light*, further exploring whether stellar brightness changed over time by analyzing historical records of stellar luminosity variations and comparing observations from different periods. This work built on the research of Gore, Pickering, Zinner, and Lundmark himself. Lundmark assumed that systematic errors in some catalogs could be treated as random errors, which enabled him to estimate the maximum possible changes in stellar luminosity and to deduce the color equation of ancient star catalogs (Lundmark, 1932d).

Based on Zinner's findings, Lundmark challenged the notion that stellar evolution, from supergiants to G-type main-sequence stars, took approximately 500,000 years. He argued that the actual evolutionary timeline was likely much longer. He analyzed different extragalactic systems, noting significant variations in their spatial distribution and suggesting that these

systems differed in age by at least 2 billion years. Lundmark grouped these systems along a temporal axis by evolutionary stage and concluded that, if stellar evolution indices such as observed luminosity or average spectral type are used, the rate of galactic evolution across the Metagalaxy would be exceedingly slow.

Lundmark then focused on nearby galaxies and globular clusters. Analyzing their luminosity data, he found no significant changes, which contradicted Zinner's conclusions. He proposed several potential explanations, including the possibility that Zinner's observed brightness changes were due to an unknown periodic phenomenon, in which stellar brightness might undergo slight fluctuations over millennia. These minor but long-term cyclical changes could explain Zinner's findings. Lundmark also suggested that the transparency of space might vary slightly in different directions, potentially influencing observed stellar brightness. While not extensively studied, this idea linked the perceived brightness changes to stellar luminosity variations (Lundmark, 1932d).

Despite results that did not support Zinner's conclusions across various time scales, Lundmark acknowledged the need for further research. He advocated examining more materials to investigate the existence of previously unknown long-period variable stars with minimal amplitudes and changes spanning thousands of years (Lundmark, 1932d).

Issues in Lundmark's Analysis of the Qing Imperial Star Catalog

Lundmark's study of the luminosity records in the *Qing Imperial Star Catalog* (*Qinding Yixiang Kaocheng*) revealed several issues. He observed that the catalog included records of stars from the Southern Hemisphere, indicating that it did not distinguish between observations made in China and those obtained from Europe. Compared with other star catalogs, the *Qing Imperial*

Star Catalog demonstrated more consistent brightness intervals, suggesting the possible use of telescopes or other equipment, as it would have been difficult to estimate the brightness of 5.8-magnitude stars with the naked eye.

Lundmark noted that Chinese astronomers and Jesuit missionaries in China both contributed to determining stellar positions, which makes it difficult to ascertain who was responsible for estimating the magnitudes recorded in the catalog. Early Chinese star catalogs lacked magnitude distinctions, and some stars listed in the *Qing Imperial Star Catalog* were beyond the naked eye's ability to estimate accurately. Consequently, Lundmark surmised that much of the catalog, including its Southern Hemisphere stars, was likely compiled with significant contributions from Jesuit astronomers such as Michel Benoist and Chinese collaborators such as Liu Songling and Bao Youguan (Lundmark, 1932b).

In 1933, Zinner received the eighth volume of Lundmark's *Lund Observatory Communications*, which included articles on the *Qing Imperial Star Catalog* and on the question of a secular change in starlight. In his reply, Zinner highlighted issues in the *Qing Imperial Star Catalog*:

Yesterday, I delved into your articles. The one on the Royal Star Catalog reminded me of studies I conducted 12 years ago. I opened the catalog, hoping to find accurate records of ancient Chinese constellations and stars, but I was greatly disappointed. Tsuchihashi Hakkentai frequently made errors in star identification, as you must have noticed. He failed to note that his identifications of Chinese constellations conflicted with both ancient Chinese sky depictions and the two accompanying star maps. He also relied on Jesuit observations of Southern Hemisphere stars. In various cases, such as entries No. 145+147, 206+212,

321+322, 329+334, and 377+378, positions of the same stars from different catalogs were conflated. Most positions were derived from Flamsteed's results.

(E. Zinner, personal communication, August 19, 1933)

Scholars such as Pan Nai echoed these observations, arguing that the primary work behind the *Qing Imperial Star Catalog* was based on corrections and calculations derived from Western star catalogs rather than on direct observations. These issues called into question the origin and accuracy of the data Lundmark used in his research (Pan, 1989).

Limitations and Contributions

Lundmark's study of ancient stellar luminosity variations did not yield as definitive conclusions or as widespread an influence as his work on ancient guest star records. This is partly because of the intrinsic nature of stars, which change luminosity extremely slowly over millions or even billions of years. While his findings were correct, his work was not without flaws. For example, Lundmark failed to recognize issues with the source material in the *Qing Imperial Star Catalog*. This oversight likely stemmed from his limited understanding of Chinese language and culture, as well as from a lack of detailed comparisons between different sources from the same period. Moreover, compared with the original Flamsteed star catalog, the *Qing Imperial Star Catalog* was less precise, reflecting the methodological challenges faced by Jesuit astronomers.

Despite these limitations, Lundmark's research highlighted the value of ancient records in the study of stellar evolution. It underscored the importance of cross-cultural scientific collaboration and laid the groundwork for further investigations into the long-term behavior of stars.

5.5 Conclusion

This chapter analyzed the extensive work Lundmark accomplished in the field of celestial evolution using ancient astronomical records. These records provided critical support for his research into the nature of novae, nebulae, and other celestial bodies, his measurement of galactic scales, and his study of stellar evolution.

In terms of measuring galactic scales, ancient guest star records supplemented Lundmark's research with additional information about novae and supernovae. These records offered clues for challenging the idea that the frequency of nova eruptions is proportional to stellar density. They also helped verify the correlation between novae and nebular material and provided valuable data for measuring the scale of the universe.

Ancient guest star records also played a significant role in Lundmark's research on nova and supernova evolution. In his studies, Lundmark discovered a substantial number of highly luminous novae in Chinese historical records. He categorized these as "supernovae" and determined, through calculations, that such celestial objects predominantly appeared in the central regions of the Milky Way. He also estimated the frequency of supernova eruptions based on related data. Additionally, Lundmark explored the possibility that the Crab Nebula originated from a supernova explosion in 1054. To this end, he actively sought Japanese historical records documenting the 1054 supernova, which supplemented existing data on its eruption time, location, and luminosity. Drawing on these materials, Lundmark confirmed that the object was indeed a supernova, making the hypothesis that the Crab Nebula originated from the 1054 supernova a reasonable deduction.

In his research on stellar luminosity variation, ancient records of stellar brightness provided essential support for Lundmark's analysis of long-term changes in stars. By studying historical observational results and by reviewing and validating previous research, he concluded that stellar evolution occurs at an extremely slow pace. However, his research also revealed some challenges, particularly his limited understanding of Chinese language and culture, which led to certain issues.

Overall, Lundmark's application of ancient astronomical records in his research allowed him to address specific scientific questions, driving advances in the field of astronomy. His work also inspired other researchers to recognize the value of ancient astronomical records and to adopt his innovative research methods. In the following chapter, this thesis further analyzes and examines the application value and reliability of historical observational records, as well as the significance of Lundmark's research methodology.

Chapter 6: Lundmark's Research Methods and the Reliability of East Asian Historical Observational Records

Lundmark's research underscores the significant value of East Asian historical observational records. This chapter analyzes the challenges in his studies of ancient guest star records and stellar luminosity changes, the impact of those challenges, and the corrections made by later researchers. It also explores the relationship between Lundmark's research and the development of modern astronomy. The chapter then reviews the origins of his ideas, discusses the insights his work offered later researchers, analyzes his research methods, and highlights the importance of historical astronomical records as supplementary observational data.

6.1 The Impact of Lundmark's Research

6.1.1 Impact on Subsequent Research in Historical Astronomy

A search of the Astrophysics Data System (ADS) for citations of Lundmark's works in historical astronomy returns 64 references to his research on ancient guest star records and 33 references to his work on stellar luminosity variations.

These studies fall mainly into two categories:

Research in the History of Astronomy

Ceragioli (1995) referred to Lundmark's findings on visual observations of stars by Ptolemy and Al-Sufi when discussing the color variations of Sirius.

Hafez (2010) cited Lundmark's research on Al-Sufi's *Book of Fixed Stars*.

Apparao (1973) incorporated Lundmark's studies in his review of the research history of the Crab Nebula.

Astronomical Research

Lundmark's analysis of ancient guest star records contributed to investigations of the relationship between novae and nebulae.

Mayall, Duyvendak, and others expanded the study of the Crab Nebula's properties (Mayall, 1962).

Bolton, Stanley, and others studied the relationship between historical supernovae and radio sources (Mayall, 1962).

The astronomical applications of Lundmark's findings can be grouped into three stages of astrophysical research:

1921–1930 (The First Stage): The Emergence and Development of Extragalactic

Astronomy

Lundmark's work on novae, their relationship with nebulae, and the frequency of nova eruptions was pivotal during this stage. He used ancient guest star records as supplementary data to reveal the spatial and distributional relationships between novae and nebulae. These records supported his measurements of intergalactic distances, nova luminosity, and eruption frequency. While certain problematic cases affected the accuracy of specific results, they did not significantly affect the overall conclusions, making *Suspected New Stars* a reliable resource for addressing the astronomical questions of this era.

1930s–1950s (The Second Stage): The Rise of Supernova Research, Radio Astronomy, Spectroscopy, and Astrophotography

Case studies during this period focused heavily on the 1054 supernova and its link to the Crab Nebula. Lundmark's *Suspected New Stars* identified the positional relationship between the 1054 supernova and the Crab Nebula. Building on this, Edwin Hubble (1928) estimated that the time required for the Crab Nebula to expand to its then-observed size was approximately 900 years. Subsequent advances in spectroscopy prompted further investigations by Mayall, Duyvendak, and Lundmark (Mayall, 1962). In 1938, Lundmark supplemented earlier findings with Japanese records translated by Yasuaki Iba, confirming the brightness of the 1054 supernova and refining earlier printing errors in his own work (Lundmark, 1938). In 1941, Duyvendak and Jan Oort definitively identified the Crab Nebula as the remnant of the 1054 supernova. In this case, Lundmark had mistakenly recorded "southwest of ζ Tauri, but very close" as " η Tauri" in *Suspected New Stars*. This erroneous entry was cited multiple times; however, because Lundmark correctly identified its location near NGC 1952, the impact of this error was minimal.

Post-1950s (The Third Stage): The Development of Radio Astronomy

In 1949, Bolton, Stanley, and Slee confirmed the Crab Nebula as a radio source. This discovery spurred interest in the connections between supernova explosions, radio sources, and first-type nebulae (often supernova remnants). Ancient guest star records, which had supported the link between the 1054 supernova and the Crab Nebula, were revisited to verify these connections (Mayall, 1962). This stage led to new demands for refining historical records. However, *Suspected New Stars* faced criticism for inaccuracies in completeness, reliability, eruption dates, and positional data. For instance, the hypothetical supernova of 827 misled many astronomers. To address these issues, astronomers and historians such as Xi Zezong, Bo Shuren, Ho Peng

Yoke, and David A. Green revisited and revised these records, adding supplementary material and analyzing individual cases from cultural perspectives.

6.1.2 Impact on the Development of Historical Astronomy

The application of ancient astronomical records led Lundmark to recognize historical records as an essential resource in astronomical research. He considered using ancient materials to address relevant problems as a methodology worth introducing into the field of astronomy. For example, in *Nya himlar* Lundmark wrote:

Det som för astronomen gör det synnerligen intressant att följa den kinesiska astronomiens utveckling och sätta sig in i dess drag är ju framför allt de många värdefulla bidrag, som kunna erhållas ur de kinesiska annalerna och som i flera fall på ett utmärkt sätt belysa även vissa moderna astronomiska problem. Även astronomhistorikern har anledning att med största intresse taga del av de högst remarkabla kinesiska observationsminnesmärkena, ty härigenom befrämjas i hög grad vad jag brukar benämna den astronomiska historiens andra uppgift, nämligen att ur äldre, ja ibland t. o. m. urgamla iakttagelser kunna få viktiga bidrag till belysandet av aktuella vetenskapliga problem i nutiden. Men astronomhistorikern skall även ur de kinesiska, i och för sig givetvis rätt sparsamma minnena, erhålla många värdefulla bidrag till den astronomiska historiens första uppgift, den uppgift som naturligtvis är gemensam med all historieskrivning, nämligen att rekonstruera förutsättningarna för astronomiens uppkomst i en given kultur, att skildra den följande utvecklingen, särskilt med hänsyn till de bärande resultat, som ha erhållits, samt klargöra betydelsen av dessa för den mänskliga

kulturutvecklingen överhuvud samt slutligen skildra astronomiens bidrag till världsbild och världsåskådning. (Lundmark, 1943, pp. 81–82)

(For the astronomer, what makes it so particularly interesting to follow the development of Chinese astronomy and to familiarize oneself with its features is, above all, the many valuable contributions that can be drawn from the Chinese annals and that in several cases admirably illuminate even certain modern astronomical problems. The historian of astronomy, too, has reason to take the greatest interest in these most remarkable Chinese observational records, for they greatly further what I am accustomed to call the *second task* of the history of astronomy — namely, the obtaining, from older and sometimes even truly ancient observations, of important contributions toward the elucidation of current scientific problems of the present day. But from the Chinese records — in themselves, of course, rather sparse — the historian of astronomy will also obtain many valuable contributions to the *first task* of the history of astronomy, the task that is naturally common to all historical writing: namely, to reconstruct the preconditions for the rise of astronomy in a given culture, to portray its subsequent development (especially with regard to the substantial results that have been achieved), to clarify the significance of these for human cultural development in general, and finally to depict astronomy's contribution to our picture of the world and our view of life.)

Lundmark regarded “extracting valuable observational results to address contemporary astronomical research problems,” what we now consider a primary goal of historical astronomy,

as part of the study of the history of astronomy. Recognizing the significance of ancient astronomical records, Lundmark actively promoted research in the field of historical astronomy throughout his career.

In 1934, Lundmark founded the Society for Astronomical Historical Research (Samfundet för astronomisk historieforskning), through which he produced numerous historical notes and papers. In 1937, to further a project within the society, he established the Tycho Brahe Astronomical Society (Astronomiska sällskapet Tycho Brahe) and articulated two main objectives for astronomical research: “to describe the relationship between the development of astronomy and general culture, and to investigate historical problems in astronomy by using ancient observational records to deepen our understanding of modern issues” (Kärnfelt, 2009).

The society actively invited astronomers and historians of science to participate in its activities. Members included figures such as George Sarton, Ernst Zinner, and the astronomer Per Collinder. In addition to the research mentioned earlier by Lundmark, Zinner, and others, the society also compiled an index of all astronomy-related topics in Sarton’s *Introduction to the History of Science*. Lundmark’s contributions to historical astronomy within the society included attempts to reconstruct star charts from different historical periods and to calculate stellar proper motion using these charts.

His work provided valuable references for the study of historical astronomy, while the society he founded served as a platform for communication and collaboration among European researchers in this field.

6.2 Lundmark's Research Methods and Value

6.2.1 Lundmark's Research Methods

Historical astronomy research is founded on ancient observational records. Researchers investigate and filter historical records, convert these observations into data suitable for modern science, and apply them to specific problems in contemporary astronomy. Lundmark's work on celestial and cosmic evolution, drawing on East Asian guest star records and historical records of stellar brightness changes, provides concrete examples of the methods used in historical astronomy. His methodology can be summarized in five key steps.

Defining the Research Problem

Lundmark began by identifying the specific problem within astronomy that his research sought to address. These problems often grew out of his own astronomical studies and were shaped by prior work in related fields. By reading widely in his research domain, he gained a sense of earlier progress and identified unresolved questions worth investigating. For example, in studying ancient guest star records, he sought to analyze the distribution patterns of novae and to understand their evolution and their relationship with nebulae. Similarly, his study of historical records of stellar brightness was inspired by Ernst Zinner's work on converting ancient brightness records, and Lundmark sought to analyze patterns in stellar brightness variation and to investigate whether changes occurred in stellar luminosity or in human sensitivity to light over long periods.

Collecting Historical Materials

After defining the problem, Lundmark gathered relevant data. Because of language barriers, he could not directly read or verify primary historical sources. His investigation of ancient guest star records therefore relied heavily on translations and compilations by researchers such as Biot, Humboldt, Williams, Zinner, Chavannes, Knobel, and Yasuaki Iba. For his studies of stellar brightness, he drew on works by Peters and Knobel (on Ptolemy's catalog), Schjellerup (on Al-Sufi's catalog), and Dreyer (on Tycho Brahe's catalog). While these sources made his research possible, they were limited in scope and sometimes contained misinterpretations because of differences between historical and modern terminology or the translators' limited astronomical expertise. These limitations led to occasional errors or omissions in his conclusions. In his study of *The Qinding Yixiang Kaocheng* star catalog, for example, Lundmark overlooked issues related to the catalog's source material, the instruments used, and their precision.

Evaluating and Analyzing the Historical Records

Once he had collected the materials, Lundmark compared different translations and analyzed linguistic nuances in the texts. Using statistical methods and contemporary astronomical findings, he assessed the reliability and authenticity of the records, selecting entries with higher credibility as novae. For his research on stellar brightness changes, he calculated the errors in the materials, analyzed their causes, and evaluated the worth of the historical records. Lundmark also considered the cultural context of the materials, recognizing that different social backgrounds and observational traditions could affect their reliability. By comparing astronomical records from various countries, he supplemented or verified specific accounts. He also studied the cultural contexts of guest star observations in China and Japan, noting the absence of magnitude distinctions in early Chinese stellar catalogs.

Data Conversion and Compilation

Lundmark compiled and summarized the filtered ancient nova records, creating a Suspected Nova Table appended to his works for future reference. In his study of historical stellar brightness, he consolidated scattered observations from various ancient texts and converted historical records into modern values. He translated data from the *Qianlong Star Catalog*, for example, into values corresponding to the Harvard Magnitude Table. He believed that similar efforts could provide valuable data for studying celestial evolution.

Applying the Data to Solve Astronomical Problems

Once the previous steps were complete, historical observational records could be used to supplement modern data and contribute to solutions for specific astronomical problems. Lundmark's research supported the analysis of the relationship between novae and nebulae, supplemented galaxy-scale measurements, investigated long-term stellar brightness changes, and helped verify the connection between supernovae and radio sources.

6.2.2 The Value of Lundmark's Historical Astronomy Research

Lundmark's methodology has significantly influenced later studies in historical astronomy. Analysis of citation data and related research content shows that his work contributed both to the study of astronomical history and to advances in astronomy.

In the study of astronomical history, Lundmark's research on ancient guest star records and stellar brightness changes has been widely cited. Researchers have drawn on his findings to investigate ancient star catalogs, the history of astronomical observation, and historical astronomical events. His work provided valuable references for exploring the history of astronomy.

In astronomy itself, Lundmark's research has been applied to questions at various stages of astrophysical research. These include studies of extragalactic systems, the relationship between novae and nebulae, nova explosion frequencies, the connection between the 1054 supernova and the Crab Nebula, and research related to radio astronomy. Lundmark was among the first to recognize the value of ancient guest star records for modern astronomical questions. Through a review of prior research, he identified unresolved issues that aligned with challenges in his own work. He then gathered and organized historical guest star records, assessed their reliability with astronomical methods, and applied them to investigate celestial evolution and nova distribution patterns. This work marked the beginning of modern research on East Asian ancient guest star records.

Through further examination of the distribution and absolute magnitudes of suspected novae in ancient Chinese records, Lundmark found that these records primarily documented objects with highly consistent maximum absolute magnitudes, which he categorized as "supernovae." He recognized their substantial value as distance indicators. He also noted the positional consistency between the Crab Nebula and the 1054 supernova, gathered additional data to validate this connection, and confirmed the Crab Nebula as the remnant of the 1054 supernova. This work contributed significantly to the study of stellar evolution. His findings inspired further interest in the Crab Nebula among scholars and led to detailed investigations of the 1054 and 1006 supernovae in Chinese records. These studies provided critical support for understanding the nature of supernova explosions and the evolution of their remnants.

Despite the significant value of his research, Lundmark faced challenges, particularly those related to his reliance on translations. The translations by Biot and Williams, for instance, contained issues such as vague comet aliases, insufficient detail on comet trajectories, and

inaccuracies in converting dates and positions, and Lundmark could not critically evaluate these aspects. Biot and Williams also drew primarily from *Wenxian Tongkao*, which is not a comprehensive summary of Chinese astronomical records, and this limited the scope of Lundmark's sources.

Later researchers, building on Lundmark's work, emphasized the importance of consulting original texts, cross-referencing multiple sources, and carefully interpreting linguistic expressions in historical records. Despite these limitations, Lundmark's detailed analysis and evaluation of historical data provided a foundation for solving practical problems in astronomy. The adoption of his research methods by later scholars highlights their pioneering nature. The continuing development of the field, including the ongoing supplementation and improvement of historical nova catalogs, demonstrates the value of using historical records to address modern astronomical challenges.

6.3 Reliability Analysis of East Asian Historical Observational Records

Historical observational records such as the Chinese *ce bu* and *hou bu* (observation registers) were used to document celestial phenomena, including solar and lunar eclipses, meteors, comets, and stellar brightness variations. These records were eventually incorporated into official dynastic histories and became essential resources for researchers such as Zinner, Lundmark, and Xi Zezong. Their reexamination of these records provided valuable insights for understanding long-term astronomical phenomena.

East Asian observational records have several advantages over those from other regions:

Long observation periods with continuity. East Asian nations have a long tradition of recording celestial phenomena. Chinese astronomical records date back to oracle bone inscriptions, and systematic observations in Japan and Korea began around 1000 CE. This continuity facilitates the study of periodic celestial events and long-term trends.

Systematic and detailed content. East Asian records cover a wide range of phenomena, including solar and lunar eclipses, planetary motions, sunspots, comets, novae, and supernovae. Observers documented precise details such as the time, location, size, and appearance of celestial events.

Focus on anomalous phenomena. The close integration of astronomy with astrology led to a heightened focus on recording unusual celestial events such as stellar brightness changes.

Unified language. After the 4th century CE, Chinese writing spread to Japan and Korea, standardizing terminology and making records from the region easier to interpret.

Challenges in Using East Asian Records

Despite their advantages, these records present challenges:

Accuracy. Observational precision varied across nations. Japanese records, for example, are generally considered less accurate than Chinese ones.

Forgery and interpretation. Some records may have been fabricated for astrological purposes, and descriptions of positions and movements are often vague.

Translation and cultural understanding. European researchers relied on translations of East Asian records, which sometimes introduced errors or misinterpretations because of linguistic and cultural differences.

The reliability of East Asian records depends on their inherent accuracy and on the researcher's ability to critically evaluate and interpret them. Cross-disciplinary collaboration with linguists, historians, and anthropologists can enhance the understanding and application of these records in modern scientific research.

6.4 Conclusion

This chapter first highlighted the significant value of Lundmark's historical astronomy research. His studies, particularly on ancient guest star records and stellar brightness changes, have been widely cited and applied to questions at various stages of modern astronomical research, offering valuable data and insights. These studies underscored the importance of historical astronomical records and encouraged Lundmark to establish institutions devoted to historical astronomy, promote his methods, and advance the development of the field. His research also faced challenges that led to certain inaccuracies, and later researchers have consulted extensive historical sources to review and refine his work, adapting it to the evolving needs of modern astronomy.

The chapter then analyzed Lundmark's research methodology and its value in detail. His approach consisted of defining research questions, collecting historical materials, evaluating and analyzing those materials, converting and summarizing observational data, and applying the results to specific astronomical problems. This methodology largely aligns with that of earlier researchers, differing primarily in the specific astronomical questions it sought to address.

Lundmark successfully evaluated and analyzed the collected data, converting it into formats suitable for modern science and thus supporting the resolution of specific problems.

His research therefore significantly influenced both the study of astronomical history and astronomy itself, providing valuable methodological references for modern astronomy.

Finally, this chapter analyzed the reliability of East Asian historical observational records. These records have several advantages, including long observation periods, broad coverage, strong continuity, and ease of interpretation. They also present challenges such as insufficient observational precision and the possibility of falsification. Before applying these records in astronomical research, researchers must critically evaluate them, considering factors such as observational precision, errors introduced during transcription, and cultural interpretation. It is also essential to compare records from different sources and apply modern scientific methods to assess their reliability, so that they can be better understood and applied.

In summary, Lundmark's research methods had a profound impact on astronomical research. The East Asian observational records he used are highly valuable and effective, but they require careful evaluation and verification before use. His work and the ancient astronomical records of East Asia together provide invaluable resources for modern scientific research.

Conclusion

Historical astronomy aims to analyze, extract, and convert ancient astronomical records into usable research data and to apply them to modern astronomical problems. Current scholarship in the field tends to focus on overviews of specific subfields and offers few case studies or sustained discussions of historical astronomy as a discipline. Existing studies of Lundmark have concentrated on his contributions to science communication and public engagement, with only brief mentions of his work in historical astronomy and his use of ancient astronomical records. This thesis seeks to fill that gap by examining Lundmark's contributions in this area.

The research draws on extensive archival work, including earlier studies on the compilation and application of East Asian astronomical records, Lundmark's own papers and books on historical astronomy, and his correspondence with other researchers in the field. Primary sources were obtained through NASA's Astrophysics Data System and the Manuscript Department of Lund University Library. Through textual analysis, case studies, and comparative research, this thesis reconstructs Lundmark's contributions to historical astronomy.

The primary aim of this thesis is to address gaps in foundational studies of historical astronomy by examining Lundmark's achievements in the field.

Lundmark's Contributions to Historical Astronomy

Lundmark's work in historical astronomy began with his *Suspected New Stars* in 1921, which remains one of his most representative studies. Archival research reveals that Lundmark's interest in historical records was driven both by his cultural curiosity and by his research needs in astronomy, inspired by the works of Humboldt, Zinner, and others.

Lundmark's research built on earlier methods while addressing different problems. While early researchers focused on celestial mechanics, such as variations in cometary orbital periods, Lundmark's work emphasized modern astronomical topics, including celestial evolution and cosmic structure. This shift explains Lundmark's focus on guest star records rather than comet records. Going beyond Biot's translations and Humboldt's commentary, Lundmark was the first to apply these records to studies of celestial evolution. His work was similar to Zinner's but distinct in its approach: while Zinner focused on post-Tycho supernovae and combined spectral analysis with modern methods to explore stellar evolution, Lundmark investigated the relationship between novae and nebulae using ancient guest star records to address questions of celestial and cosmic evolution.

After *Suspected New Stars*, Lundmark expanded his research to include historical records of stellar magnitudes. He also analyzed nova and supernova frequencies and explored their luminosities, nature, and evolutionary processes. Additionally, he investigated the cultural symbolism of novae and comets, using astronomical perspectives to study links between historical figures and celestial phenomena. These studies provided valuable references for subsequent researchers and highlighted the close relationship between historical astronomy and modern astronomy.

Lundmark's Methodology and Impact

Lundmark's methodology involved defining research problems, collecting sources, evaluating and analyzing records, converting and summarizing observational data, and applying these data to solve specific astronomical questions. Compared with earlier researchers, Lundmark emphasized careful linguistic analysis of historical records and used modern astronomical

knowledge to assess their reliability. Despite these strengths, his reliance on translations and limited scrutiny of data sources occasionally led to inaccuracies, such as in his studies of guest star records and historical stellar magnitudes. For example, his work on *Qinding Yixiang Kaocheng* lacked critical analysis of data origins and did not cross-check sources, which affected the reliability of his findings.

Nonetheless, Lundmark's research significantly influenced historical astronomy. His efforts encouraged the establishment of related research institutions and inspired other researchers to recognize the value of ancient astronomical records and to adopt similar methodologies. His work demonstrated the feasibility of applying historical data to address modern astronomical questions, paving the way for advances in both astronomy and historical astronomy.

Broader Applications of Ancient Astronomical Records

Ancient astronomical records have proven highly valuable for historical astronomy. Long-term observations of phenomena such as solar and lunar eclipses, comets, novae, sunspots, and stellar magnitudes have supplemented contemporary observations, aiding in the solution of specific astronomical problems. These records have facilitated studies in various fields, including celestial mechanics, climate science, and chronology. For example, researchers have used historical records to analyze cometary physical characteristics, calculate orbital periods, and predict returns; to correlate sunspot records with climatic changes; and to verify the authenticity and timing of historical events.

Before Lundmark, researchers such as Pingré, Herschel, and Hind had compiled and analyzed cometary records, while others such as Fritz and Maunder had investigated ancient sunspot records. After Lundmark, scholars such as Xi Zezong, Ho Peng Yoke, Clark, and Stephenson

further examined East Asian guest star records, producing more reliable star catalogs and addressing new questions in celestial evolution. For example, Stephenson used historical eclipse records to study Earth's rotation. These case studies underscore the enduring relevance of ancient astronomical records for addressing contemporary scientific challenges.

Recommendations and Final Thoughts

This study highlights the strong applicability of ancient astronomical records to astronomy. Lundmark's pioneering work in historical astronomy, combined with his innovative methodologies, provided valuable references for subsequent researchers and advanced the development of both astronomy and historical astronomy. His research demonstrated the potential of historical records to contribute critical data to modern scientific inquiries.

Moving forward, researchers should deepen their investigations into the specific applications of historical records, critically evaluate their reliability, and address existing issues in their interpretation and use. Cross-disciplinary collaboration involving linguists, historians, and astronomers can further enhance the analysis and application of these records, unlocking their full potential for modern science.

In conclusion, ancient astronomical records remain a crucial resource for astronomy, offering insights that bridge the historical and modern scientific worlds. Lundmark's contributions exemplify the transformative power of integrating historical data into contemporary research, providing a model for future exploration and innovation in the field.

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